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Deliverable 3.3

Final design of real-time control and VNF intelligence mechanisms

Abstract

D3.3 is the third deliverable within DAEMON WP3 documents, hence building on D3.1 and D3.2, and focusing on near-real-time, real-time, and in-network functionalities. This deliverable outlines the final design of 13 NI solutions distributed across four WP tasks: compute-aware radio scheduling, multi-timescale edge resource management, reconfigurable intelligent surfaces, and in-backhaul support for service intelligence. The document offers a high-level overview of these solutions, their alignment with the DAEMON architecture in WP2, and planned WP5 experiments for validation. Each NI solution is detailed with a WP2 requirement mapping and architectural insights, concluding with future directions of how the WP3 footprint relates to the ongoing activities on the next generation of mobile networks.

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	11
2	Native integration of WP3 Algorithms in the WP2 architecture.....	12
2.1	Native integration of WP3 Algorithms in the DAEMON architecture from WP2.....	12
2.1.1	Machine Learning (ML) Pipeline.....	12
2.1.2	Network Intelligence Orchestrator.....	13
2.2	WP2 procedures in action: conflict resolution.....	14
2.2.1	Conflict resolution in the RAN.....	14
3	Compute aware radio scheduling.....	16
3.1	Reliable distributed unit for virtualization.....	16
3.1.1	Solution description.....	16
3.1.2	Integration with the NI native procedures.....	16
3.1.3	Requirement satisfaction.....	17
3.2	ML Radio Resource Scheduling for virtualized RANs.....	17
3.2.1	Solution description.....	17
3.2.2	Integration with the NI native procedures.....	23
3.2.3	Requirement satisfaction.....	23
3.3	Cloud acceleration for vRANs.....	23
3.3.1	Solution description.....	24
3.3.2	Integration with the NI native procedures.....	27
3.3.3	Requirement satisfaction.....	28
3.4	Application aware radio scheduling.....	28
3.4.1	Solution description.....	28
3.4.2	Integration with the NI native procedures.....	31
3.4.3	Requirement satisfaction.....	31
3.5	Compute-aware scheduling analytics VNFs.....	32
3.5.1	Solution description.....	32
3.5.2	Integration with the NI native procedures.....	34
3.5.3	Requirement satisfaction.....	34
4	Multi-timescale edge resource management.....	35
4.1	AI-enhanced edge orchestration.....	35
4.1.1	Solution description.....	35
4.1.2	Integration with the NI native procedures.....	35
4.1.3	Requirement satisfaction.....	36
4.2	WLAN performance prediction for spectrum management.....	36
4.2.1	Solution description.....	37
4.2.2	Integration with the NI native procedures.....	37
4.2.3	Requirement satisfaction.....	38
4.3	Energy aware edge resource management (UMA).....	38
4.3.1	Solution description.....	38
4.3.2	Integration with the NI native procedures.....	40
4.3.3	Requirement satisfaction.....	41
4.4	Data-driven resource orchestration.....	43
4.4.1	Solution description.....	43
4.4.2	Integration with the NI native procedures.....	43
4.4.3	Requirement satisfaction.....	43
4.5	Multi-timescale network slice reservation.....	44
4.5.1	Solution description.....	44
4.5.2	Integration with the NI native procedures.....	45

4.5.3	Requirement satisfaction.....	46
5	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS) control.....	47
5.1	RISMA.....	47
5.1.1	Solution description	47
5.1.2	Integration with the NI native procedures.....	49
5.1.3	Requirement satisfaction.....	49
6	In-backhaul learning.....	50
6.1	Random Forest models in programmable switches.....	50
6.1.1	Solution description	50
6.1.2	Integration with the NI native procedures.....	52
6.1.3	Requirement satisfaction.....	52
6.2	Efficient backhaul circuit switching	52
6.2.1	Solution description	52
6.2.2	Integration with the NI native procedures.....	53
6.2.3	Requirement satisfaction.....	53
7	Outlook towards 6G.....	54
7.1	Access.....	54
7.1.1	O-RAN Hardware Acceleration Abstraction Layer	54
7.2	Core.....	54
7.2.1	Release 17.....	54
7.2.2	Release 18.....	55
7.3	Management and Orchestration (TID, IMEC)	55
8	Conclusions	57
9	References	58

List of Figures

Figure 1. The Network Intelligence Plane (NIP) and the functional blocks of the Network Intelligence Orchestrator and ML pipelines [3].	12
Figure 2. The integration of the NIFs detailed in Sections 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3, using the N-MAPE-K approach.	14
Figure 3. The conflict resolution procedure for the chosen example.	15
Figure 4. The ML radio resource scheduling solution overview.	17
Figure 5. ATHENA throughput and the regions of the distilled decision tree.	21
Figure 6. Critic's reward prediction for SNR = 20 dB and congestion factor $\beta=0.6$.	21
Figure 7. Machine Reasoning in network management and orchestration.	22
Figure 8. Congestion factor re-orchestration by ATHENA-MR to satisfy KPI.	22
Figure 9. Mean (line) and max-min range (shaded area) latency and energy to decode an LDPC-encoded TB. Intel FlexRAN LDPC library on an AVX512-accelerated Intel Xeon Gold 6240R CPU core @ 2.40GHz; and a commercial driver on an NVIDIA V100 GPU.	24
Figure 10. CloudRIC high-level architecture. Extensions to the O-RAN standard are highlighted in red.	25
Figure 11. Detailed architecture of CloudRIC.	26
Figure 12. CloudRIC's Greedy LPU allocation algorithm.	26
Figure 13. Comparison of the performance of traditional and L4S congestion control on the 5G test bed (top) and on WiFi (bottom).	30
Figure 14. Impact of L4S on the RLC buffer occupancy evolution for the four traffic classes considered (mobile1 transports video, mobile2 web, mobile3 podcast and mobile4 bulk data transfer), (left) without L4S, (right) with L4S.	30
Figure 15. System model including the local/cloudlet classifiers and predictors. Each device is constrained by its average power budget, and the cloudlet has a limited computation capacity.	32
Figure 16. The online task outsourcing algorithm called OnAlgo.	33
Figure 17. Average optimality gap and constraint violation of OnAlgo.	33
Figure 18: The different ways fairness can be enforced in a time-slotted dynamic system. The decision maker can either consider the α -fairness objective $F\alpha$ at every timeslot (slot-fairness) or at the end of the time horizon T (horizon-fairness).	44
Figure 19. OHF policy.	45
Figure 20: RISMA: RIS-aided Multi-user Alternating Optimization.	48
Figure 21. Henna architecture mapped into the ingress and egress PISA pipeline.	50
Figure 22. Joint packet- and flow-level classifier example.	51

List of Tables

Table 1. Reliable Distributed Unit (DU) usage of the interfaces.....	16
Table 2. Reliable Distributed Unit (DU) for virtualization. Requirement satisfaction.....	17
Table 3. ML Radio Resource scheduling usage of the interfaces.....	23
Table 4. Reliable Distributed Unit (DU) for virtualization. Requirement satisfaction.....	23
Table 5. Comparison of processors for 5G LDCP loads.....	24
Table 6. CloudRIC usage of the interfaces.....	27
Table 7. Cloud acceleration for vRANs. Requirement satisfaction.....	28
Table 8. Reliable Distributed Unit (DU) usage of the interfaces.....	31
Table 9. Application-aware radio scheduling. Requirement satisfaction.....	31
Table 10. Compute-aware scheduling analytics VNFs usage of the interfaces.....	34
Table 11. Compute-aware scheduling analytics VNFs. Requirement satisfaction.....	34
Table 12. Usage of internal interfaces for AI-enhanced orchestration.....	35
Table 13. AI-enhanced edge orchestration. Requirement satisfaction.....	36
Table 14. WLAN performance predictor usage of internal interfaces.....	37
Table 15. WLAN performance prediction for spectrum management. Requirement satisfaction.....	38
Table 16. SAVRUS usage of the interfaces.....	40
Table 17. Energy-aware edge resource management. Requirement satisfaction.....	41
Table 18. Data-driven resource orchestration usage of the interfaces.....	43
Table 19. Data-driven resource orchestration. Requirement satisfaction.....	43
Table 20. Multi-timescale network slice reservation usage of the interfaces.....	45
Table 21. Multi-timescale fairness in networks. Requirement satisfaction.....	46
Table 22. RISMA usage of the interfaces.....	49
Table 23. RISMA. Requirement satisfaction.....	49
Table 24. RF models in programmable switches usage of the interfaces.....	52
Table 25. Flow-level Random Forest models in programmable switches. Requirement satisfaction.....	52
Table 26. Efficient backhaul circuit switching usage of the interfaces.....	53
Table 27. Efficient backhaul circuit switching. Requirement satisfaction.....	53

List of Acronyms

3GPP – 3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G – Fifth Generation
5GC – Fifth Generation Core
5G-NR – 5G New Radio
AAL – Acceleration Abstraction Layer
AAL-B – Acceleration Abstraction Layer Broker
AAL-B-CP – Acceleration Abstraction Layer Broker Control Plane
AAL-B-UP – Acceleration Abstraction Layer Broker User Plane
AAR – Application-aware RAN
AC – Actor Critic
ACK – acknowledgement
ADRF – Analytics Data Repository Function
AF – Application Function
AI – Artificial Intelligence
AnLF – Analytics Logical Function
AP – Access Point
API – Application Programming Interface
AQM – Active Queue Management
B5G – Beyond 5G
BS – Base Station
CB – Contextual Bandit, Contextual Bandit, or Code Block (depending on context)
CPU – Central Processing Unit
CRC – Cyclic Redundancy Check
CSI – Channel State Information
CUPS – Control plane – User plane Separation
CWR – Congestion Window Response
DCCF – Data Collection Coordination Function
DDbS – Diversified Distance-Based Sampling
DDPG – Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient
DT – Digital Twin
DU – Distributed Unit
ECE – ECN Congestion Experienced
ECN – Early Congestion Notification
E-HARQ – Early - Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request
eMBB – Enhanced Mobile BroadBand
FEC – Forward Error Correction
FIFO – First-In-First-Out
gNB – next generation Node B
GNN – Graph Neural Network
GPU – Graphics Processing Unit
HA – Hardware Accelerator
HARQ – Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request
IETF – Internet Engineering TaskForce
KNN – K-nearest neighbor
KPI – Key Performance Indicator
L4S – Low-Latency Low Loss Scalable throughput
LCS – Location Services
LDPC – Low-Density Parity Check
LDR – Local Reachability Density
LOF – Local Outlier Factor
LPU – Logical Processing Unit
MAC – Multiple Access Control Layer

MANO – Management and Orchestration
MAPE-K - Monitor, Analyze, Plan, Execute and Knowledge
MCS – Modulation and Coding Scheme
MFAF – Message Framework Adaptation Function
ML – Machine Learning
MNO – Mobile Network Operator
MR – Machine Reasoning
MSE – Mean Squared Error
MTLF – Model Training Logical Function
NFV – Network Function Virtualization
NI – Network Intelligence
NIF – Network Intelligence Function
NIF-C – Network Intelligence Function Component
NIO – Network Intelligence Orchestrator
NIS – Network Intelligence Service
NWDAF – Network Data Analytics Function
O-DU – Open Distributed Unit
O-RAN – Open Radio Access Network
OHF – Online Horizon Fair
OGA – Online Gradient Ascent
OGD – Online Gradient Descent
ONOS – Open Network Operating System
PFD – Packet Flow Descriptions
PHY – Physical Layer
PRB – Physical Resource Block
PUSCH – Physical Uplink Shared Channel
QA – Quality Attribute
QUIC – Quick UDP Internet Connections
RAN – Radio Access Network
RED – Random Early Drop
RB – Resource Blocks
RIC – RAN Intelligent Controller
RIS – Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RL – Reinforcement Learning
RLC – Radio Link Control
RMSE – Root Mean-Squared Error
RT – Real-Time
RTT – Round Trip Time
RU – Radio Unit
SBA – Software Based Architecture
SBI – Service Based Interface
SCS – SubCarrier Spacing
SD-WLAN – Software Defined Wireless Local Area Network
SDO – Standard Development Organizations
SNR – Signal-to-noise ratio
SRS – Statistical Recursive Search
TB – Transport Block
TCP – Transmission Control Protocol
TL – Transfer Learning
TNA – Tofino-Native Architecture
TTI – Transmission Time Interval
UDP – user datagram protocol
UE – User Equipment

UL – Uplink

UPF - User Plane Function

URSP – UE-Route Selection Policies

VNF – Virtual Network Function

VR – Virtual Reality

vRAN – virtualized Radio Access Network

WLAN – Wireless Local Area Network

Executive summary

This final deliverable of a series presents the progress achieved by DAEMON partners in designing and developing multiple Network Intelligence (NI)-assisted functionalities, as outlined in Objective 2 of the Grant Agreement. The primary focus is on near-real-time, real-time, and in-network functionalities. In D3.1 [1], we initially introduced eleven (11) Beyond Fifth Generation (B5G) problems, and in D3-2 [2], we introduced two (2) additional problems. In total, this document provides detailed information on thirteen (13) NI-assisted functionalities, addressing challenges across all four tasks within WP3:

1. Compute-aware radio scheduling
2. Multi-timescale edge resource management
3. Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces
4. In-backhaul support for service intelligence

More specifically, Section 1 outlines the key results of this deliverable, mapping them to the specific objectives of the work package. Then, in Section 2, we go deeper into how the different activities of the work package have been integrated into the overarching WP2 architecture, specifically discussing how the NI native procedure detailed in D2.3 [3] has been considered in the WP3 work. To conclude this section, we also define how two Network Intelligence Functions (NIFs) defined in this deliverable are synchronized with each other using one specific NI procedure (i.e., conflict resolution).

In Sections 3 to 6, we present the latest advances on the NI-assisted functionalities. For each of these sections, we report the technical description, their integration with the NI procedures defined in D2.3 [3], explicitly discussing how the NIFs are leveraging the interfaces towards the NI orchestration framework and an exemplary definition of how the NIFs integrate with the procedures. Finally, we also update the fulfillment of the requirements as defined in Task 2.1

More in detail, Section 3 discusses compute-aware radio scheduling solutions. We total 5 solutions, most of them intertwined, as they are solving problems related to the matching of the available computing capacity to the radio tasks to be performed. These solutions, moreover, have been designed to perfectly integrate with the major network architectures defined by standards, such as 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) and Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN).

Moving on to Section 4, we consolidate the discussion about all NI-assisted functionalities within the context of multi-timescale edge resource management. The proposed 5 NIF functionality targets different aspects of edge computing ranging from the prediction of Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) performance to the specific orchestration of such infrastructure, leveraging also learning-based and data-driven solutions.

Section 5 is dedicated to joint control of radio base station beamforming and Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS) configuration. Here, we present RISMA, a non-AI (Artificial-Intelligence) solution that transforms a non-convex formulation into a problem solvable with classical semidefinite relaxation techniques, resulting in sub-millisecond execution times without requiring fitting data.

Finally, Section 6 introduces solutions for two problems within the scope of in-backhaul learning. They are targeting the integration of the intelligent at the intelligence very close to the u plane, directly in the circuit switching procedure. For these solutions, the capability of achieving sub-millisecond latency is fundamental, as we also demonstrate in the forthcoming deliverable for WP5 where many of the WP3 solutions have their implementation in a real system.

Before concluding in Section 8, we discuss in Section 7 how the activities in WP3 align with the current and ongoing trends in the standardization activities, for the three domains that are targeted by WP3 activities: Radio Access Networks, Core Networks, and Management and Orchestration. Through this discussion, we reflect how the work on the next generation of mobile network relates to the footprint of the work package work, mostly shaped around papers and demonstrators in top-tier conferences and journals.

Finally, Section 8 provides the closing remarks summarizing the main takeaways of this deliverable.

1 Introduction

This deliverable reports the final design of the NI-based functionality for (Near-) Real-Time control and vNF (Virtual Network Function) Intelligence. Besides the description of the specific algorithms, the goal of this document is thus discuss the achievements and progress of the objectives related to WP3, as well as showcase the interaction with other WPs. In particular, the objectives of the WPs included:

- “Objective 2: Developing specialized NI-assisted network functionalities for B5G systems”. WP3 contributed to this objective by defining 13 Network Intelligent Functions (NIFs) that have been discussed and described in this document and in the two previous versions of deliverables D3.1 [1] and D3.2 [2]. These could be further classified into two main categories, as detailed by the following sub-objectives:
 - “Sub-Objective 2.1 – Developing Network Intelligence (NI)-assisted functionalities for B5G performance and efficiency”. Among the algorithms designed by WP3, many of them are directly targeting the improvement of some specific metrics related, e.g., to the wireless capacity increase or the reliability of the system.
 - “Sub-Objective 2.2 – Developing NI-assisted functionalities that enable the sustainable operation of B5G systems”: in conjunction with the development of specific NI functionality for performance, some NIFs designed by WP3 also incorporate sustainability aspects related to energy and resource savings.
- “Objective 4: Demonstrating the viability and performance of NI-native B5G networks”. The Network Intelligence Algorithms developed in WP3 provided specific Key Performance Indicator (KPI) validation, which has been carried out in the context of WP5.

In addition, WP3 contributed to two specific sub-objectives

- “Sub-objective 1.2 – Enabling NI deep into the edge and user plane” as different NI algorithms are acting at the edge of the network (like in the radio access network) to and directly into the user plane (such as the in-backhaul learning solutions).
- “Sub-Objective 3.3 – Developing AI models for adaptable NI” following the guidelines of WP2 as already reported in D2.1, as well as the orchestration procedures.

All these objectives have been achieved, as we discuss in this Deliverable. In Section 2, we detail how the WP3 algorithms implement the generic framework discussed by the NI Orchestration (NIO) procedures in D2.3 [3]. Sections 3,4 and 5 specify the information related to the 13 proposed NI functionalities, detailing the information in a structured way. For each functionality, we discuss:

- The solution description, including updates or further definitions with respect to the previous WP3 deliverables.
- The integration with the Network Intelligence Orchestration (NIO) defined by WP2, including the usage of the interfaces defined by the NIO framework and the orchestration procedures as discussed in D2.3.
- The fulfillment of the Functional Requirements specified in Task 2.1, with the percentage of accomplishment and the rationale behind the specific performance requirements completeness.

By following this approach, we consistently discuss all our innovations in a common framework, explaining how they build up towards the DAEMON view.

Finally, Section 7 provides an outlook towards 6G. As we discuss there, many concepts and solutions that we devised in WP3 have also been studied and integrated by major Standard Development Organizations (SDOs), which will be the fundamental building blocks of the next generation of Mobile Networks.

2 Native integration of WP3 Algorithms in the WP2 architecture

D2.3 [3] defined the final version of the DAEMON project NI Native architecture and the procedures that constitute the way of interacting with the architecture. While in Sections 3, 4, 5, and 6, we detail how every NIF defined in WP3 leverages the different interfaces and architectural modules, in this Section we discuss: i) the fulfillment of the general requirements from an architecture point of view towards the WP3 specificities, and ii) the possible implementations of some guidelines specified in WP2 about the co-existence of different NIFs at the same time in the network.

2.1 Native integration of WP3 Algorithms in the DAEMON architecture from WP2

The NIFs targeted by WP3 envision the integration of Network Intelligence that is deployed very close to the user plane or the edge of the network, which operate in real or near-real-time timescales.

Figure 1. The Network Intelligence Plane (NIP) and the functional blocks of the Network Intelligence Orchestrator and ML pipelines [3].

Figure 1 above illustrates the key functional blocks defined by the DAEMON architecture, which have been specifically designed to facilitate the seamless integration of NI within network operations. In the following discussion, we will delve into how these specific components are utilized by the solutions proposed in WP3.

2.1.1 Machine Learning (ML) Pipeline

The ML procedures play a vital role in preparing data-driven models that enable the implementation of the various functionalities envisioned by the project. From the perspective of WP3, this aspect must consider two key characteristics:

- The rate of incoming data, which can be significantly high. For instance, at the far edge, consider a 5G Distributed Unit (DU) that has to take scheduling decisions based on data coming from several Radio Units (RUs). Therefore, it is essential for the training of algorithms, like Reinforcement Learning (RL), to occur independently from the network operations, ensuring decoupling between the two.
- The registered models need to be sufficiently flexible so as to adapt to potentially changing conditions, such as those encountered in the radio domain. In this regard, it is crucial to explore the possibility of leveraging continuous training across different scenarios to improve the extendibility of the different models. An example of such a model is the one related to the Machine Learning Radio Resource Scheduling discussed in Section 3.2, which is constantly monitored by the conflict resolution engine discussed in Section 2.1.2.4, such that it can be replaced according to the changing environmental condition (e.g., more congested computing resources).

2.1.2 Network Intelligence Orchestrator

The NIO plays a pivotal role in facilitating the lifecycle management of network intelligence within the DAEMON project. Working in tandem with the NIF Managers and the NIF Component Manager, which handle lower-level factors such as container management for specific intelligence components, the NIO encompasses several modules that are of paramount importance within the scope of WP3.

2.1.2.1 *Analytics and Monitoring*

Similar to the ML pipeline discussed earlier, effective monitoring of intelligence deployed at the edge is crucial for ensuring proper system operation. This monitoring task, carried out by numerous solutions developed in WP3, plays a vital role. By collecting metrics related to the performance of intelligence algorithms (such as precision and accuracy for classification algorithms or errors for forecasting algorithms), the NIO can assess the behavior of NIFs or specific NIF Components (NIF-C). Consequently, appropriate actions can be taken if performance degradation occurs. These actions may include selecting a new model from the catalog or implementing corrective measures.

For instance, a possible countermeasure to reduce the effects of suboptimal decisions taken by NI algorithms that are leveraging on models that do not represent the network context anymore, is to temporarily disable such action taking, applying them in a "sandbox", and understand what are the input contexts that cause such misbehaviors. This will help to identify what actions are causing conflicting decisions.

However, achieving real-time monitoring of these operations is challenging due to the fast decision-making pace of WP3 algorithms.

2.1.2.2 *Knowledge Management*

The generalization of ML models holds immense significance in dynamic and rapidly changing environments, particularly in the edge network being studied in WP3. It allows the models to adapt and perform effectively without the need for frequent re-training or extensive model modifications. In these fast-varying environments, where conditions and data distributions can rapidly shift, Machine Learning (ML) models with strong generalization capabilities excel at handling such variations while consistently providing accurate results. Nevertheless, achieving generalization requires the analysis of large amounts of data input data for training purposes, which could be difficult depending on the type of network functions (especially for access functions that have a large amount of input variables to take into account).

ML models are trained to capture the underlying patterns and dynamics of the network. This empowers them to make accurate predictions and informed decisions even in the face of previously unseen scenarios. Avoiding constant re-training results in significant savings in computational resources and minimizing disruptions to network operations.

Consequently, the development of ML models with robust generalization capabilities [4] becomes a critical factor in enabling efficient and reliable performance within fast-varying environments like the radio access network. In this context, effective knowledge management, including continuous exchange of information between different intelligence algorithms running in various parts of the network, can significantly enhance the generalization of these models. This collaborative approach to knowledge management enhances the overall network operation by leveraging collective intelligence and improving the generalization capabilities of ML models.

2.1.2.3 *Explainability*

AI and ML interpretability is a rapidly growing field that has garnered significant attention in recent times [5][6]. The interest in explainability lies in evaluating learned models and building trust among their users. However, despite the evaluation of AI and ML methods using specific metrics, a consensus on the definitions of interpretability and explainability is yet to be reached. Various disciplines are actively studying this problem [7]. Currently, it remains unclear what characteristics are essential for the interpretation of a black-box model in order to generate outputs that are relevant to a specific user or problem [8]. In DAEMON, we support this view by including an explainability and interpretability module in the NIO design.

As we discuss more in detail in Section 3.2.2, we propose the concept of "actionable" Machine Reasoning (MR) [9][10][58], which involves making additional decisions based on the ones already taken by AI/ML models. This approach is particularly suitable for managing 5G networks, as this task operates on a different time scale compared to other AI/ML-based operations. This concept is a good fit, e.g., for the O-RAN ecosystem, as it natively applies to the different modules of the system, as already discussed in [2]. We leverage these techniques to analyze the behavior of underlying AI/ML rApps/xApps/dApps and dynamically re-orchestrate resources to meet operator-defined requirements in the context of a ML-based radio resource scheduling algorithm.

2.1.2.4 Conflict resolution

In the NI vision defined by the project, multiple NIFs work collaboratively to establish a Network Intelligence Service (NIS) that optimizes and coordinates a suite of NIFs toward a shared objective, such as sustainability. However, coordinating these algorithms may introduce short transients where the decisions made by each algorithm could deviate due to factors like data distribution shifts, inference glitches, or slightly misaligned loss functions during training. In such situations, the DAEMON NIO plays a crucial role in configuring policies to address conflicts and mitigate potential issues before the system aligns itself with the overall service goal or requires model amendments or re-training. In the subsequent section, we delve into the specific approach taken by the NIO to arbitrate between two algorithms defined by WP3, demonstrating how this coordination is implemented.

2.2 WP2 procedures in action: conflict resolution

As defined in [3], Section 5.1.2, the NIO provides a conflict resolution procedure for algorithms that act on the same sink, according to the N-MAPE-K definition. We exemplify this for two algorithms described in this document: the Reliable Distributed Unit (DU) solution (Nuberu), discussed in Section 3.1, and Radio Resource Scheduling algorithm (ATHENA), described in Section 3.2.

2.2.1 Conflict resolution in the RAN

Figure 2. The integration of the NIFs detailed in Sections 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3, using the N-MAPE-K approach.

As depicted in Figure 2, both algorithms in question utilize similar data sources, necessitating coordination. However, their primary interaction occurs at the MAC scheduler in the DU of 5G base stations, which serves as a common Sink. On the one hand, the Reliable DU algorithm (Nuberu) performs two main functions. Firstly, it predicts the probability of successful decoding of uplink frames, leveraging information from the L1 layer to mark frames as decoded or undecoded even before the actual decoding process takes place. Secondly, it modulates the number of uplink grants available to the Media Access Control Layer (MAC) scheduler to compensate for decoding operations that may not be accomplished in time due to fluctuations in computing capacity.

Conversely, the ML Radio Resource Scheduling algorithm (ATHENA) determines the number of Resource Blocks (RB) and the Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) to be used at a given point in time, ensuring that the time budget allocated for decoding operations is not exceeded. These two algorithms complement each other well as they both aim to achieve the same goal, with each emphasizing the strengths of the other.

However, conflicts may arise between them in certain situations. For example, Nuberu may reduce decoder capacity due to a previous failure to meet the time deadline, while the ML scheduling algorithm assumes full computing capacity within the system. Since the capacity reduction information is only available after the congestion control algorithm of Nuberu, and not during the scheduling phase, this conflict cannot be anticipated beforehand by ATHENA.

Nevertheless, by leveraging the explainability capabilities of the ML Radio Scheduling algorithm, as discussed in Section 3.2.1 (Figure 5), we can observe that, while the RL agent in the dAPP makes decisions that push the boundaries of the reward distribution, such as maximizing overall throughput, there are areas where simpler and "failsafe" decisions can be considered. These decisions become relevant when Nuberu needs to scale down and alleviate congestion at the L1 decoder.

Two possible decisions can be made to reduce the scheduled Transport Block (TB)¹ in the uplink: reducing the number of RBs or reducing the applied MCS. By utilizing the information available in the explainability module of the scheduler, the conflict resolution policy can regenerate the grants based on this new policy until the congestion is resolved, enabling both algorithms to resume normal operation. The conflict

¹ A Transport Block (TB) is the basic MAC-layer user data unit, with variable bit size.

resolution policy is formalized as follows and depicted in Figure 3. The conflict resolution procedure for the chosen example below:

1. The ML scheduling algorithm continuously provides explainability measurements to the NIO for periodic policy updates in case of conflicts (i.e., two disjoint MAC scheduling decisions).
2. During each policy update, the conflict policy is injected back into the K module of the ML algorithm, which is responsible for adjusting the initially made decisions.
3. When congestion control is detected, the Nuberu computes the maximum TB size that can be scheduled for the next Transmission Time Interval (TTI), as described in Section 2.1 of [3].
4. This information is then communicated back to ATHENA, which needs to revise the previously made decision that assumed full capacity, considering the current congestion level.
5. The conflict policy is used to determine the best combination of MCS and RBs that maximizes the reward while adhering to the constraint on the maximum available TB size.
6. Grants are reformulated based on these constraints.
7. The revised grants are scheduled.

During the conflict resolution operation, no explainability information is reported to the NIO, only information regarding the utilization of the conflict resolution scheme.

According to this scheme, both algorithms can operate without issues, reaching their optimal point of operation. However, if congestion persists for an extended period, resource re-orchestration is required, which will be triggered by the NIO using the NIO-MANO (Management and Orchestration) interface.

Figure 3. The conflict resolution procedure for the chosen example.

3 Compute aware radio scheduling

In this section, we complete the information about the NI Functions already introduced in D3.1 and D3.2. Where applicable, we provide more details about the solutions. Otherwise, we refer to the specific subsection in the previously issued documents.

3.1 Reliable distributed unit for virtualization

3.1.1 Solution description

The complete solution, Nuberu, was described in D3.2 [2], Section 2.1.

3.1.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

3.1.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 1. Reliable Distributed Unit (DU) usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	Through this interface, the algorithm discussed in D3.2 [2], Section 2.1 reports the current statistics for the network operation, which are then used to possibly trigger a re-training of the whole system. In detail, the metric that is reported is the accuracy ratio for the Early - Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (E-HARQ) process. Also, other internal metrics, such as the number of delayed decoding, are communicated through this interface, to take further action in case of system congestion (e.g., providing more resources)
Nio-Nifcm	This interface is used to orchestrate the different components of the algorithm: e.g., the probes to get network information, the Application Programming Interface (API) to enforce the scheduling decision, and the intelligent components for the Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) process. In the reference implementation detailed in D5.2 [11], Section 4.1, we use a standalone approach, but the different elements can have an independent lifecycle.
Nifm-Nifnis	Besides the standard creation and termination procedures, this interface is used to inject different configuration policies into the system (e.g., the parameters of the E-HARQ algorithm)
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface is used together with the Nio-Nifcm to update the hardware resources associated with the function. As this solution does not use Neural Networks, resource re-orchestration for this NIF is unlikely to happen.
Nio-MLp	N/A (this solution does not require training)
Mlo-Ncat	N/A (this solution does not require training)
Nio-MANO	Through this interface, the Nio can issue re-orchestration requests to the vRAN system in case excessive delay is experienced due to a lack of computing capacity.
Nio-Ext	This interface communicates to other O-RAN components, as detailed in D3.2 [2], Section 2.1

3.1.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We detail in this subsection how this solution leverages the NIF management procedure discussed in Section 5.1.3 of D2.3 [3].

1. This procedure is initiated if the E-HARQ process starts to misbehave (e.g., the accuracy of the system drops below a certain threshold, like 99.9999%). Hence, through the NIO, it decides to use a new value for the E-HARQ procedure.
2. By looking into the NIS Catalog, it selects a new version that uses a more conservative value (e.g., frames are more likely to be discarded if uncertain). This will create more re-transmission at the MAC layer but less at the RLC/transport layer.
3. Models are validated and submitted to the Open Distributed Unit (O-DU) through the Nio-Ext and Nifm-Nifnis interfaces.
4. The O-DU system acknowledges the new parameters.

3.1.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 2. Reliable Distributed Unit (DU) for virtualization. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
FR-CAWRS-000	Successful (100%)	This requirement is about the introduction of reliability algorithms. As discussed in Section 2.1 of [2] and demonstrated in Section 4.1.1 of [11], the reliability has been increased by a factor of 2.
FR-CAWRS-001	Successful (100%)	The predictive HARQ mechanism, which has been introduced in Section 2.1.3.3.1 of [2] and validated in Section 4.1.1 of [11], fulfilled this requirement.
FR-CAWRS-002	Successful (100%)	The congestion control algorithm has been discussed in Section 2.1.3.2.2 and 2.1.3.3.2 of [2]. Validation results for such algorithms is available in Section 4.1.1 of [11]

3.2 ML Radio Resource Scheduling for virtualized RANs

3.2.1 Solution description

Figure 4. The ML radio resource scheduling solution overview.

The solution discussed in this Section, ATHENA [55], creates a closed control loop taking scheduling decisions based on contextual information coming from the Radio Access Network (RAN), e.g., the UE-associated (User Equipment) wireless channel conditions, and from the cloud provider’s data center monitoring system, e.g., the current β . ATHENA then transforms this information into scheduling policies, optimizing RAN performance to the hard time deadlines imposed by the computing platform.

We formulate our problem as a Contextual Bandit (CB) problem, in which in each episode $t \in T$, the agent receives the current context $c(t)$ as a feature vector drawn from a context distribution C . The agent then chooses and executes an action $a(t) \in A$, where A is the action space, and receives a reward $r(c(t), a(t))$ from the execution environment. The reward distribution over the $(c(t), a(t))$ pair is considered unknown a-priori.

The CB problem can be considered a particularization of the full RL problem, with the context c in CB analogous to the state s in RL. However, while the next context $c(t+1)$ in CB is independent of $c(t)$ and $a(t)$, in RL, the distribution of $s(t+1)$ depends both on the last state and on the performed action. This observation matches our setup since the context, which includes the channel conditions and congestion factor, is not affected by the scheduling decision. Also, while reward estimation in RL requires accounting for future rewards using a discount factor γ , the reward in CB equals the instantaneous collected reward. Therefore, any CB problem can be solved using RL algorithms considering 1-step episodes or alternatively $\gamma = 0$.

ATHENA uses an RL algorithm to solve the CB problem by adjusting it to 1-step episodes. The resulting policy function $\pi(c): \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$ is a deterministic function that maps the current context into action. The goal is to learn the optimal policy

$$\pi^* = \arg \max_{\pi \in \Pi} [r(c, \pi(c))],$$

which maximizes the received reward. ATHENA is also model-free, in the sense that it does not have any insights about the environment's internal model. On the contrary, it relies solely on the received reward signal, which renders ATHENA an appealing solution for heterogeneous computational platforms.

3.2.1.1 ATHENA components

1) Context Space C:

Let $c \in \mathcal{C}$ denote the system context, where the context space \mathcal{C} in ATHENA incorporates the combination of

- i. the congestion $\beta \in \mathcal{B}$, where \mathcal{B} is the set of eligible congestion factors of size $|\mathcal{B}|$, and
- ii. the UE's channel conditions $\bar{c} \in \mathcal{R}$, approximated via UE's Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR).

The first variable can be measured by the cloud provider metrics system, while the second is usually considered by state-of-the-art Radio Resource Schedulers. We define

$$c(t) := (\beta(t), \bar{c}_u(t))$$

to be the context vector representing the system's context at stage t . We then define the context space as $\mathcal{C} := \mathcal{B} \times \mathcal{R}$.

2) The action space A:

As existing radio resource schedulers [12], ATHENA takes two consecutive decisions: First, an assignment of a number of Physical Resource Blocks (PRBs) $n_u \in \mathcal{N}$ for UE u . Second, a selection of an MCS over those PRBs, to match the UE channel conditions. Let $m_u \in \mathcal{M} := \{1, \dots, M\}$ be the MCS decision for user u , where \mathcal{M} is a set of possible MCS that is available by the 5G radio technology.

Thus, we define the action space $\mathcal{A} := \mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{M}$, essentially capturing all possible pairs of decisions $m_u(t)$ and $n_u(t)$ allocated to user $u \in \mathcal{U}$ in decision episode t .

The scheduling decision/action is transferred to the user and modulates the Uplink (UL) frame accordingly. The environment is the computational platform and, more specifically, the Low-Density Parity Check (LDPC) decoder, which decodes the UL frame and gives back the reward signal.

3) Rescaling the action space for scalability:

In the configuration above, \mathcal{A} increases linearly with the number of PRBs N . Especially for certain 5G deployments of 100 MHz and SubCarrier Spacing (SCS) 30 KHz, N equals 250, which is five times more than in the case of 10 MHz and SCS 15 KHz, showcasing the need for an efficient representation of the action space. To avoid this, we move from discrete decision variables $\alpha_u(t) = (n_u(t), m_u(t))$ to continuous $\hat{\alpha}_u(t) = (\hat{n}_u(t), \hat{m}_u(t))$. By doing so, we simplify the ML task by making the action selection problem continuous, namely a regression one. That is, the outcome variable is a continuous variable in the 2-D space, which we discretize to space $\mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{M}$. By moving to the continuous space, we manage to associate adjacent actions, which cannot happen in the discrete space where every action is distinct.

4) Reward function:

Given the \bar{c}_u condition for each user u and the congestion factor β , we encourage the actions a that will probably lead to successful decoding, ultimately pushing the system to learn allocations that result in high system throughput. Successful decoding happens when

- i. the data bits are transmitted without any errors under the SNR conditions and
- ii. T_{dec} does not exceed the deadline.

Higher (n_u, m_u) combinations imply carrying more data with fewer redundant bits for error correction. Depending on the channel conditions and system congestion, this can lead to decoding failures after I_{MAX} iterations and deadline violations.

We design ATHENA's reward function to account for this observation. Our reward captures the contribution of

- i. the data bits $d_u(t)$ that user u is granted by the next generation Node B (gNB) to transmit under action a at u ;
- ii. a binary variable $r_u(t)$ denoting the result of the Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC) of the TB after decoding it;
- iii. the decoding time $T_{dec,u}(t)$ for the TB and
- iv. the target decoding deadline J .

More specifically:

$$R = \begin{cases} d_u & \text{for } T_{dec,u}(t) \leq J - 1 \text{ and } r_u = 1 \\ -K, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

where K is a positive constant term for penalizing wrong decisions. Thanks to this approach, ATHENA learns quickly because it takes advantage of both CRCs' values and decoding time.

3.2.1.2 ATHENA internal design

1) Actor-critic design:

ATHENA is solving the CB problem using a 1-step episode RL architecture that follows the Actor-Critic (AC) paradigm [13], which has shown superior scalability properties [[13], Chapter 13.1]. AC belongs to the policy gradient family of algorithms, can operate on continuous-valued control spaces and directly approximate the best policy function π across the reward r obtained by each state-action pair, and thus its direct applicability to the Fifth Generation (5G) New Radio (5G-NR) systems, especially the one based on O-RAN. On the other hand, value-based algorithms (e.g., SARSA, Q-Learning, DQN etc.) operate on distinct control spaces, approximate the state-value or the action-value function and then apply an ϵ -greedy selection policy on the control space. This becomes intractable in big action spaces, such as in large bandwidth 5G deployments.

We opted for the Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) [14] algorithm due to its benefit in resolving deterministic continuous action problems. The DDPG agent comprises two functions: the actor and the critic. The critic approximates the action value function $Q(c, a)$ that predicts the expected reward, which is received by the environment when performing action a in context c . The critic is represented by a neural network $Q_\phi(c, \alpha)$, parameterized by weights ϕ . Given a set of interactions D consisting of samples (c, a, r) , it minimizes the residual Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the predicted $Q_\phi(c, \alpha)$ and the received reward r :

$$E_{(c,\alpha,r) \sim D} [(Q_\phi(c, \alpha) - r)^2]. \quad (3.2.1)$$

The actor approximates the policy function. It is represented by a neural network μ_θ , with weights θ , and gives the deterministic action $\hat{a} = \mu_\theta(c)$. The goal of the actor is to output the action \hat{a} that maximizes $Q_\phi(c, \hat{a})$ so that:

$$E_{c \sim D} [Q_\phi(c, \mu_\theta(c))]. \quad (3.2.2)$$

2) Actor inference:

As we mentioned in Sec. 3.2.1.A.3, for scalability reasons, we rescaled the output action so that the actor gives the approximate continuous $\hat{a} = (\hat{n}, \hat{m})$ instead of the discrete $\alpha = (n, m)$. In order to discretize \hat{a} , we implemented the following hierarchical blocks [15]:

- 1) *Action Generation*: We applied the K-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN) function

$$g_k(\hat{a}) = \arg \min_{\alpha \in A}^k |\alpha - \hat{a}|^2,$$

where k denotes that the k actions in A , that are closest to \hat{a} by L_2 distance, are returned.

- 2) *Action Refinement*: Even though the actions are close to each other in A , they may have a completely different impact on the environment, and blindly choosing the closest to \hat{a} is not ideal. For example, in low SNR conditions, if the MCS component \hat{m} of the output of the actor is 9.8, then selecting the closest $m = 10$, which applies 16-QAM modulation, instead of $m = 9$, which applies QPSK modulation and therefore severely lower complexity, may have a detrimental effect on the decodability of the frame. Hence, we evaluate each of the k actions and select the highest reward according to the prediction of the critic.

$$\pi_{\theta, \phi}(c) = \arg \max_{\alpha \in g_k(\mu_\theta(c))} Q_\phi(c, \alpha) \quad (3.2.3)$$

3) Application to O-RAN and 5G-NR standards:

As depicted in Fig. 4, ATHENA acts on several components of the 5G-NR and O-RAN architectures. Indeed, ATHENA acts in the MAC layer of the 5G-NR stack, supporting the decisions of the scheduler at every TTI. We require this location to cope with fast-changing conditions on the radio channels since speeds up to 120 km/h and 500 km/h for vehicles and high-speed vehicles, respectively, have to be supported, according to the 5G standard [16]. Frequent user scheduling at every TTI to provide high throughput and low latency and high 5G high bands incur high SNR variations within very few TTIs, as discussed in [17]. This requires rapid reactions from the gNB side to maintain high throughput by achieving decodability and staying within the deadline constraints. We place ATHENA in the MAC layer of the O-DU directly in inference, hence being able to support very fast responses from the model, while the training can be performed in the near-RT RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC), decoupled from the user plane.

For episode i at TTI t , the HARQ process (residing in the MAC layer) queries ATHENA with the context c_i and receives the scheduling action a_i . The action is enforced in the Physical Uplink Shared Channel

(PUSCH) channel at TTI $t + J$, and the reward from the LDPC decoder r_i is collected at TTI $t + 2 \cdot J$. Because of the nature of the HARQ processes, a single acting agent would suffer from the delayed reward problem; at TTI $t + 1$, the agent has to take action for the episode $i + 1$, before the reward of the i -th episode is collected.

We leverage the independent lifecycle of each HARQ's data transmission and demultiplex the DDPG agent into $|H|$ agents, as many as the HARQ processes. We name them HARQ agents and they share the same parameters θ, φ . Each agent i interacts with the HARQ process i . At each TTI t , we assign the agent indexed by $t \bmod |H|$ to handle the transmission. Following the same procedure, the decoder returns the reward to the corresponding agent. Since the HARQ agents interact with the HARQ (MAC) and the decoder (PHY), which require fine time resolution, we fit them in the Distribution Unit (DU) of the O-RAN architecture.

We also offload the learning functions of the HARQ agents to a main agent. The main agent shares the same model parameters with the HARQ agents. At every scheduling opportunity, the HARQ agents store the samples, consisting of context, action and reward (c, a, r) in their internal buffer. At periodic timings, the main agent collects these samples over the E2 O-RAN interface, calculates the gradients, optimizes the model, and pushes back to the DU the updated weights. Since the sample collection does not have strict timing constraints, the main agent can reside either on Near-RT or Non-RT RIC. In Fig. 4, we depict how ATHENA integrates with the O-RAN architecture. We have placed the main agent running as an xApp in the Near-RT RIC and the HARQ agents running in O-DU as dApp, adopting a concept from [18].

4) Offline Training:

O-RAN principles require pretraining of the agent models before they are deployed on a live production environment [19]]. To comply with this requirement, we collected a dataset D from an isolated sandboxed environment with multiple samples for randomly taken scheduling decisions $\alpha(t) = (n(t), m(t))$ and contexts $c(t) = (\beta(t), \bar{c}(t))$ where we recorded the decoding time T_{dec} and the CRC result r as returned by the LDPC decoder. In order to accelerate training, reduce the sample complexity and remove unavoidable outliers produced by a real system, we grouped per (β, \bar{c}, n, m) and modified the returned reward for each group as follows:

$$R^{group} = \begin{cases} d_w, & \text{if } P[r = 1] \geq r_{thres} \text{ and } T_{dec}^\gamma \leq J - 1 \\ -K, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

where T_{dec}^γ is the γ -percentile $\in [0, 1]$ of T_{dec} within the group, and we consider it as a proxy for performance vs. reliability trade-off. Due to the stochastic nature of the computing platform, there is high variability of the decoding times, which can be accounted for measurement imperfections, incapability to isolate the low-level caches of the processors, virtual memory invalidation during context switches etc. Picking higher γ would lead to learning more conservative policies because of the negative reward, and vice-versa.

With r_{thres} , we set a target threshold value above which we can consider satisfactory data transmission in terms of successful error correction.

3.2.1.3 Explainability through Machine Reasoning

Another block of ATHENA is the Machine Reasoning (MR) part, which interprets the results of the ML and devises (at a slower pace) actionable decisions on the network. The model has to provide insights into its internal functionality and decision process, which we call explanations. These explanations are categorized into three different classes depending on the question that they seek to answer [20]: the attributive, the contrastive, and the actionable explanations. In the study we conducted, we investigated methods for all three categories, and we adjusted them accordingly to our NN-based actor-critic architecture.

1) Attributive Explanations:

The attributive explanations answer to the question of why, given an input, the model gave a certain outcome. These insights touch both the input, e.g., features of a particular example, as well as the internals of the model (splitting rules in the case of a decision tree, neurons in the case of neural networks, etc.). They provide a comprehensive correlation between the input and the output, which does make sense for an external observer. This categorization mainly comprises feature importance methods such as LIME [21]] and SHAP [22]], which are model-agnostic explainers. Model distillation is another method that can be used to produce explanations. The key concept behind this is to distill a black-box model (such as a neural network) into an inherently better explainable surrogate model. This class of surrogate models typically comprises shallow decision trees and linear models, whose parameters (splitting criteria and variable coefficients, respectively) are generally admitted to be better understandable. The distillation process consists of two models, namely the teacher T and the student S . T is the black-box trained model for which the explanations are asked. S is a smaller surrogate model that integrates the knowledge of T while maintaining its accuracy.

ATHENA's model, which is described in Eq. 3.2.3, consists of two neural networks: the actor's μ_θ , which provides an approximate solution $\hat{\alpha}$, and critic's Q_ϕ , which assists in refining it to α . We distill the actor's model to a regression tree, which is a decision tree that holds linear models in its leaves (instead of constant approximators). We used response-based knowledge distillation [23], where S mimics only the T's output layer. During the training process, T (actor) and S produce outputs $\hat{\alpha}_T, \hat{\alpha}_S \in \mathbb{R}^2$, respectively. In order to train the tree S, we pass these outputs through the interpolation function $h: \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. This interpolation function is created using TBS as the target value of combinations (n, m) . The outputs $h(\hat{\alpha}_T), h(\hat{\alpha}_S)$ are used to compute the distillation loss, which in our case is the -distance, capturing the difference in yielded throughput between T and S. In fact, we use the teacher's predictions as target values and we train the decision tree S in a supervised way, using the distillation loss as split criteria. We trained with maximum tree depth 3, in order to make it easier to interpret.

Figure 5. ATHENA throughput and the regions of the distilled decision tree.

In Figure 5, we depict the achieved throughput of the agent for combinations of the contextual features, and with the red dashed-edged rectangles, we paint the borders of the leaves of the trained decision tree. We interpret the splitting thresholds in order to understand the internal decision process of the actor. The tree has divided the input space into 4 regions, in which the NN-based actor can be approximated by a linear model. These areas have a specific meaning in the context of a vRAN system. For congestion factors $\beta > 0.5$ (Region 4), the actor yields the same throughput independently of the channel conditions. That is, the Central Processing Unit (CPU) is so congested that ATHENA is forced to scale down consistently both the MCS and PRB for all channel conditions. For lower β , instead, the SNR is taken into account and for values higher than 20 dB, the agent is divided into 2 different models so that the maximum achievable throughput can be more finely approximated.

2) Contrastive Explanations:

Contrastive explanations answer the criticism of why not a different result is the outcome of the AI system.

Figure 6. Critic's reward prediction for SNR = 20 dB and congestion factor $\beta=0.6$.

To adapt this question to our case study, we look for the explanation for a specific decision taken by ATHENA: *given a certain context c, why has a = (n, m) been scheduled instead of a' = (n', m')*? To answer this question, we leverage the architecture and resort to the objective function of the actor in Eq. 3.2.2, i.e., to maximize the reward prediction of the critic. Querying the critic $Q_\phi(c, \alpha)$ and $Q_\phi(c, \alpha')$ and comparing the reward expectation provides a quantitative explanation of the actor's decisions. For example, in Figure 6, for the contextual state $\beta = 0.6$ and $\bar{c} = 20$ dB, we show the critic's reward prediction for all possible actions. From the figure, we can see that the ATHENA actor learns one of the actions that yield the highest predicted reward, effectively approximating in its internal variables where the negative reward area (i.e., a frame not decoded in time) is hit. It is important to clarify that the agent outputs directly the best action, and not all the possible actions, which would be intractable.

3) Actionable Explanations:

Actionable explanations seek to answer how the input of the model should be modified so that a certain user-defined desired outcome is achieved. The change to be made is otherwise called *counterfactual*. This category of explanations is of particular importance from the network perspective because it allows not only understanding the system but also taking further decisions (e.g., re-orchestration decision) to steer the system to a desired operational state, effectively implementing the vision depicted in Figure 7.

There may exist multiple counterfactuals that answer the question above, but we only consider the counterfactual that requires the smallest possible change [24].

For this analysis, we hence focus on a specific counterfactual orchestration decision: what should be changed in the virtualized RAN (vRAN) setting so that the throughput that ATHENA achieves is at least thr_{target} (e.g., a throughput KPI in an Enhanced Mobile BroadBand (eMBB) scenario)? From the network orchestration perspective, the only variable that the operator can control is the vRAN's CPU congestion factor β , since the user's channel conditions depend on many exogenous factors related to the UE characteristics. Because setting the minimum β is the obvious answer, we introduce a sustainability clause in the cost function $C(\beta) : R \rightarrow R$ of operating at a certain β , measured in monetary units, that forces the system to operate the system using the cheapest solution in terms of computing capability. Although the specific shape of this cost function can be very complex, we only draw a simple requirement constraining $C(\beta)$ to be a monotonically decreasing function. This is motivated by real systems, as high β implies the usage of a less expensive CPU (in terms of executed instructions per second) or a higher concentration of competing jobs on the same CPU set as the one the vRAN is running on in a CPU sharing fashion. In this context, the counterfactuals are produced as a solution to the following optimization problem [24]:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\beta \in B} \quad & C(\beta) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & thr_{ATHENA}^\beta \geq thr_{target} \end{aligned} \tag{3.2.6}$$

where the constraint assures that the throughput achieved by ATHENA thr_{β} ATHENA at congestion factor β satisfies the target. The MR block of ATHENA, namely ATHENA-MR, analyzes the different input states over a time window in order to take further decisions that target the optimization of e.g., the computing resources. Consequently, the MR part runs in the Non-RT (Real-Time) RIC, optimizing the orchestration by:

- i. orchestrating the gNB decoder threads to a more congested CPU to save operational costs, or
- ii. taking the opposite decision when they are running in a too congested infrastructure and the performance is not acceptable anymore.

To solve the optimization, we devised a simple heuristic. A replica of the ATHENA ML agent exists in the Non-RT RIC. We act reactively and consider the user's minimum SNR over the last window, i.e., the worst-seen channel condition, iterate over the possible $\beta_i \in B$, infer ATHENA's achievable throughput and retrieve the minimum β that satisfies the constraint in Eq. 3.2.6.

To showcase the capability of the MR block to re-orchestrate the congestion factor, we consider a UE at full buffer demand and we modify the gain G of the channel periodically between 0.5 and 0.12 for 200 s. The time window over which MR operates is 30 s and initially $\beta = 0$, i.e., operating at maximum operational cost. In order to mimic a network orchestrator that has to decide among a finite set of possible actions (e.g., assigning a given number of CPU cores, each of them with a specific capacity), we set the feasible set of possible actions equal to $B = \{0, .1, .2, \dots, 1\}$.

Expanding or restricting the feasible set affects the running time of ATHENA-MR, which is linear to the number of elements and its running time is trivial to the time window. We consider 3 different scenarios with 3 desirable throughputs: 8, 13, and 17 Mbps. In the top row of Figure 8, we show in black the SNR per PRB and in red the re-orchestrated β . In the second row, we show the achieved throughput and the target throughput with a straight line.

In all three scenarios, the MR block re-orchestrates the computational resources to save operational costs and satisfy the constraints. We observe that in the case of 8 Mbps target throughput, the congestion factor is only once modified since the target can be reached at both SNR levels. At a target of 13 Mbps, β is accordingly adjusted, but throughput violations occur when the SNR drops

Figure 7. Machine Reasoning in network management and orchestration.

Figure 8. Congestion factor re-orchestration by ATHENA-MR to satisfy KPI.

since the orchestration algorithm has not yet reacted to the contextual changes. Finally, in the last scenario of 17 Mbps, the minimum throughput cannot even be reached because of the low SNR. However, the MR reacts best-effort and lowers the congestion factor to 0, before recovering back to 0.2 when the SNR increases back again.

In Figure 4, we see how a closed loop using MR is shaped. The O-DU informs ATHENA-MR about the worst-seen SNR over the last time window via the O1 interface, which solves the optimization problem based on the ATHENA model and service requirements and sets the computing resources in the O-Cloud via the O2 interface.

3.2.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

3.2.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 3. ML Radio Resource scheduling usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	The algorithms report through this interface the current statistics related to the operation of the intelligent components. As we discussed in Section 2.2.1, all the metrics related to explainability are reported back to the Nio, through this interface, and the conflict resolution policy is inserted.
Nio-Nifcm	The implementation of these components was initially reported in D5.2 [11], Section 3.1.1, and will be further discussed, also with the addition of Digital Twin (DT) capabilities in D4.3.
Nifm-Nifnis	This interface is used to inject, e.g., the conflict resolution policies in the Knowledge component of the algorithm.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface is used to estimate the current congestion level and to update the operation of the NI solution.
Nio-MLp	This interface is used to issue possible re-training of the system due to changing conditions. This can also be performed using a DT of the network infrastructure.
Mlo-Ncat	The created models are pushed into the catalog through this interface.
Nio-MANO	The machine reasoning solution discussed in the following subsection uses this interface to issue re-orchestration of the system resources in case of too-long malfunction of the system.
Nio-Ext	This interface communicates to other O-RAN components, as detailed in D3.2 [2], Section 2.5

3.2.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

As discussed in Section 2.1.2.3, explainability is handled by the NIO to support operations such as conflict resolutions in the system. In the following, we explain how this is leveraged by ATHENA. In a nutshell, by leveraging techniques from the Machine Reasoning literature, we introduce the explainability of our AI model, thus enriching the NIO operation. More specifically, the NIO is now able to explain why for a given input, the AI model took the decisions that it took, why it did not take other decisions, and how the input of the model should be modified so that a certain desired outcome is achieved. Moreover, this concept is suitable in the O-RAN ecosystem, as it natively applies to the different modules of the system, as already discussed in [D3.2]. The details related to the explainability procedures are detailed in Section 3.2.1.3.

3.2.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 4. Reliable Distributed Unit (DU) for virtualization. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
FR-CAWRS-000	Successful (100%)	As discussed in Section 3.2.1, this NI Functionality introduces NI in different elements of a DU to attain reliability.
FR-CAWRS-002	Successful (100%)	The NI algorithm discussed in Section 3.2.1 performs radio resource scheduling according to the available computing capacity. Further validation results will be available in D5.3.

3.3 Cloud acceleration for vRANs

3.3.1 Solution description

A key component of O-RAN 5G base stations is the DU that performs physical layer (PHY) tasks, including Forward Error Correction (FEC). DU functions must meet strict compute time guarantees since the signal processing pipeline they contribute to has hard deadlines in the 1-3 ms range. These deadlines must be met with 99.999% probability (5-nines) to provide reliability, as otherwise users may lose synchronization and drop network connectivity. Yet, FEC involves heavy operations that hampers conventional virtualization approaches. For instance, Figure 9 (left) shows that FEC's LDPC decoding tasks in a high-end CPU can take over 1-3 ms just to process one user's TB, thus compromising the pipeline latency budget.

Figure 9. Mean (line) and max-min range (shaded area) latency and energy to decode an LDPC-encoded TB. Intel FlexRAN LDPC library on an AVX512-accelerated Intel Xeon Gold 6240R CPU core @ 2.40GHz; and a commercial driver on an NVIDIA V100 GPU.

The industry today: DU-dedicated Hardware Accelerators (HAs). In order to address the problem above, vRAN solutions on the market today resort to offloading compute-intensive FEC tasks to a dedicated Hardware Accelerator (HA) co-located with every DU. Traditional HAs are ASICs (e.g., Intel ACC100) and FPGAs (e.g., Intel PAC N3000), but Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) (e.g., NVIDIA Aerial) have also been recently considered. These HAs can provide >10× performance gains over CPUs when processing large TBs, as illustrated in Figure 9 (left) for a GPU-based HA, and are indispensable to abide by the latency specifications for DU operations. However, such high-performance HAs are expensive, as exemplified in Table 1. Moreover, HAs are energy-hungry, as shown in Figure 9 (right) for a GPU-based HA. More broadly, an Intel ACC100 ASIC and an NVIDIA V100 GPU consume up to 52W and 250W, respectively, i.e., 20-82% of the overall consumption of a commodity server. In fact, the economic and energy costs of DU-dedicated HAs are so high that they have sowed doubts in the industry about building vRANs using this approach.

Our proposal: HA/CPU pooling across DUs. We propose a more efficient vRAN approach that reduces costs without sacrificing reliability, and helps dispelling the doubts above. It combines two approaches.

HA pooling. HAs co-located with (and thus exclusively used by) individual DUs suffer from low utilization under real workloads. We seize this opportunity to share HAs among multiple DUs, so as to amortize the cost of these expensive resources, and provide the needed acceleration at an affordable cost per DU. While conceptually simple, HA pooling across DUs for PHY tasks is extremely challenging from a technical viewpoint. It requires harnessing real-time multiplexing opportunities at the millisecond timescales at which both PHY functions are executed and user traffic varies. 71% of US operators intend to realize RAN pooling solutions by 2025 [28], and some have already implemented it, but traditional RAN centralization approaches only exploit long-term traffic variations, such as day-night ones, which is insufficient for reliable and cost-efficient RAN virtualization. Our proposal also goes well beyond the current capabilities of the O-RAN standard. O-RAN's Acceleration Abstraction Layer (AAL) provides appropriate abstractions to pool HA resources, but AAL can neither coordinate access from multiple DUs nor enforce (compute-aware) radio policies, two features that are critical to providing reliability on dense platforms.

Table 5. Comparison of processors for 5G LDPC loads.

	CPU core	GPU	FPGA	ASIC
Programmable	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Time-To-Market (months)	<2	<2	2	30
Non-Recurrent-Engineering cost (\$)	0	0	0	350K-1000K
Unit cost (\$)	110 (Intel Xeon 6240R as of Dec. 2022)	8000 (NVIDIA V100 as of Dec. 2022)	4000 (Intel PAC N3000 as of Dec. 2022)	3000 (Intel ACC100 ASIC as of Dec. 2022)

Opportunistic HA offloading. CPUs are usually ignored to bear FEC workloads in carrier-grade RANs because of their poor latency performance, as explained before. Instead, we argue that they can be a valuable complement to HAs in those tasks and propose to leverage heterogeneous computing resources for DU operations as a way to substantially improve the cost-efficiency of vRANs. The rationale is again straightforward: as minimizing the latency of FEC operations brings no benefit as long as deadlines are met, CPUs may be exploited on specific occasions to alleviate the energy toll of HAs. As an example, Figure 9 (left) shows that a CPU core can decode TBs below 50 Kb within the often adopted 3-ms deadline, and Figure 9 (right) shows that this operation consumes 1.45 nJ per bit per decoding

amount of expected energy $\hat{e}_k^{(i)}$ is selected. The result is communicated to the AAL-B-UP (to route the grant) and to the relevant queue time estimator (to update its estimate).

(6) LPU processing. After $K2$ slots, the UE transmits the TB corresponding to the scheduled grant $g^{(i)}$. The DU forwards the received TB to the AAL-B-UP's dispatcher, which routes the data to the pre-assigned AAL Queue for FEC processing. LPUs process queued TBs in a First-In-First-Out (FIFO) manner. Once decoded, the data is sent to the DU, and the corresponding queue time estimator in the AAL-B-CP is updated.

3.3.1.2 Radio policy agent

CloudRIC's radio policy agent shall produce grants that are conscious of the current pressure on the LPUs and of the added load brought by the new requests. In turn, these properties depend on the specific hardware and software settings of the network environment (e.g., the number, type, and detailed specifications of the LPUs, which substantially affect the performance as we saw in D3.1, Section 4.2, and are stateful (i.e., are contingent on the utilization of LPUs at the moment of the radio scheduling decision). Hence, they are hard to model in advance, and require a solution that automatically adapts itself to the target O-RAN system upon deployment.

In light of this consideration, we resort to a data-driven model that can learn the tangled relationships above at runtime. We implement the radio policy agent as a *soft actor-critic* deep reinforcement learning (RL) algorithm under a twofold rationale: (i) the RL paradigm allows training the model online from system observations directly and (ii) inference is achieved with a simple neural network (the actor) that involves trivial arithmetic operations to minimize inference latency, as later proven in D5.3. Among many actor-critic instances, we opted for a soft version that maximizes the reward while acting as randomly as possible to explore the solution space during training.

The instantaneous reward function used by the critic is

$$R^{(i)} = \begin{cases} \left(t^{(i)} / \bar{t}^{(i)} \right) \cdot \alpha & \text{if } w_n^{(i)} + d_n^{(i)} < D - \delta \\ -\beta \cdot \alpha & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Two cases are possible. If TB $g^{(i)}$ is processed within a guard period δ to the deadline D , the decision is assigned a positive reward proportional to the granted fraction of the requested TB $(t^{(i)} / \bar{t}^{(i)})$ scaled by a factor α . Otherwise, deadline violations yield a penalty β , also scaled by α .

3.3.1.3 LPU models

The purpose of the LPU models $\{v_n, \mu_n\}$ is to estimate the processing latency, without queuing effects, and the energy consumption of each processor in the pool, for a given grant $g^{(i)}$. This is a stateless task, hence, the LPU models can be easily built offline with data collected in a pre-calibration phase. Indeed, we take this approach in our implementation of CloudRIC, employing the measurement data presented in D3.1, Section 4.2, to train LPU models for the specific LDPC drivers and GPU/CPU LPUs considered there.

We realize the LPU models as simple feed-forward neural networks, which are accurate and efficient universal function approximators. An important remark concerns the loss function used to train the models. For the energy estimator μ_n , we use a legacy Mean Absolute Error (MAE) loss to minimize the absolute error. However, the loss for the processing latency estimator v_n has a dedicated design that stems from the following consideration. Underestimating $\hat{d}_n^{(i)}$ risks violating deadlines, which incurs significant throughput loss and poor spectrum usage; conversely, overestimating $\hat{d}_n^{(i)}$ only implies far less disruptive radio resource under-allocations. Therefore, it is critical that the LPU model never underestimates latency, while still trying to minimize overestimation. Let the latency prediction error for grant $g^{(i)}$ be $\epsilon_n^{(i)} := \hat{d}_n^{(i)} - d_n^{(i)}$, $\forall n \in \mathcal{L}$; the WCET loss is then expressed as

$$L(\epsilon_n^{(i)}) = \begin{cases} -\lambda \cdot \epsilon_n^{(i)} & \text{if } \epsilon_n^{(i)} \leq 0 \\ \epsilon_n^{(i)} & \text{if } \epsilon_n^{(i)} > 0, \end{cases}$$

where $\lambda > 1$ allows mitigating optimistic predictions.

3.3.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

3.3.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 6. CloudRIC usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	Through this interface, the algorithm discussed in Section 3.3 reports the current statistics for the network operation, which are then used to possibly trigger a re-training of the whole system. In detail, the metric that is reported is the average empirical reward of the RT-RIC every 100-1000ms.

Nio-Nifcm	This interface is used to orchestrate the different components of the algorithm: the RT-RIC's agent, and the AAL-B's LPU models, queue time estimators and LPU allocator.
Nifm-Nifnis	Besides the standard creation and termination procedures, this interface is used to inject different configurations of CloudRIC, such as the desired latency deadline.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface is used together with the Nio-Nifcm to update the hardware resources associated with the NIF, which in turn will trigger a re-training process of the LPU models.
Nio-MLp	This interface is used to issue possible re-training procedures for either of the two learning agents (RT-RIC's radio agent and AAL-B's LPU models) due to changing conditions.
Mlo-Ncat	The created models are pushed into the catalog through this interface.
Nio-MANO	Through this interface, the NIO can issue re-orchestration requests to the vRAN system, in case the system observes overly low throughput.
Nio-Ext	This interface communicates to other O-RAN components: O-DUs to interact in real-time with their MAC layer and the SMO.

3.3.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We detail in this subsection how this solution leverages the NIF management procedure discussed in Section 5.1.3 of D2.3 [3].

1. This procedure is initiated when the network throughput observed by the NIO is below a certain threshold. In this case, the NIO can either relax the processing deadline or use the Nio-Ext interface to request O-RAN SMO more computing resources.
2. In either case, the NIO looks into the NIS catalog for a new set of RT-RIC radio agent and LPU models that correspond to the new scenario. If none exist, a re-training process is triggered.
3. Models are validated and submitted to the O-Cloud via the Nio-Ext and Nifm-Nifnis interfaces.
4. The O-Cloud system Acknowledges the new parameters.

3.3.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 7. Cloud acceleration for vRANs. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
FR-CAWRS-000	Successful (100%)	The solutions detailed in 3.3.1.2 efficiently introduce a NI solution in a vRAN system. Performance evaluation results will be available in D5.3.
FR-CAWRS-002	Successful (100%)	Through the models described in Section 3.3.1.3, the intelligent algorithms described in Section 3.3.1.2 can effectively jointly manage the allocation of computing and radio resources in real-time. Performance validation results will be available in D5.3.

3.4 Application aware radio scheduling

3.4.1 Solution description

3.4.1.1 Introduction

In deliverables D3.1 [1] and D3.2 [2], we proposed various traffic classification algorithms that base their decision on the evolution of the Radio Link Control (RLC) queue occupation, which we further evaluated in deliverables D5.1 [59] and D5.2 [11]. The performance of the best of these algorithms was excellent, with an accuracy of 95% or more.

In the labeled data that we captured to train and test the algorithms, the RLC buffer was not controlled by any Active Queue Management (AQM) algorithm. Only if the queue is full (radio) packets are dropped, and only then the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) controlled applications in the endpoints adjust their sending rate (i.e., their throughput). Remark that nowadays, most applications are TCP controlled, with the exception of applications that are controlled by the Quick UDP (User Datagram Protocol) Internet Connections (QUIC) protocol, which uses a similar congestion control protocol as TCP.

Recently, new queue management strategies have been proposed that allow offering Low-Latency Low Loss Scalable throughput (L4S) [25][26][27] to applications (e.g., Virtual Reality (VR)). With these new queue management strategies, the evolution of the RLC buffer is heavily impacted, which we illustrate below, and hence, possibly also the performance of the classification algorithms proposed earlier.

First, we describe the basic principles of L4S and how they impact the RLC buffer occupancy. Then, we investigate the impact of L4S on the traffic classification algorithms.

3.4.1.2 *L4S principles*

After various congestion collapses, congestion control was implemented in TCP. The congestion control the Internet Engineering TaskForce (IETF) currently mandates is based on maintaining a congestion window controlled via the “slow start” and “congestion avoidance” algorithms (see [28]). TCP’s congestion control increases its congestion window (and, hence, its throughput), either exponentially during “slow start” or linearly during “congestion avoidance”, until it detects packet loss, either under the form of a triple duplicate acknowledgment (ACK) or a time-out. After the former, it halves its congestion window, while after the latter, it resets the congestion window (close) to the initial congestion window.

Relying on the tail drop for packet loss turned out to have some adverse side effects, e.g., synchronized TCP flows and large queue occupancies (also referred to as “bufferbloat”). Therefore, AQM techniques were recommended to be used [29]. Initially, Random Early Drop (RED) was proposed, which controls the buffer occupancy, but it was realized that it is more fruitful to control the queuing latency instead [30][31]. Additionally, it was noticed that AQM did not have to drop packets, but could instead mark them, a technique referred to as Early Congestion Notification (ECN). For that purpose, two bits were reserved in the IP header and two bits in the TCP header [32].

Initially, a marked packet was considered to be semantically equivalent to a dropped packet: when a receiver notices a marked packet, it sets the ECM Congestion Experienced (ECE) bit in all the ACKs it sends; upon reception of one ECE marked ACK the sender reduces the congestion window (as if a triple duplicate ACK was received) and sets the Congestion Window Response (CWR) bit in the next packet to send, notifying the receiver to stop setting the ECE bit in the ACKs it sends. In that way, TCP reacts once per Round Trip Time (RTT) when packets are marked.

Later it was realized that ECN could be used to signal congestion more accurately. This was first proposed to be used in a data center environment in [33]: rather than setting the ECE bit until the CWR bit is received, the receiver, in principle, echoes in the ECE bit if a received packet was marked or not. It needs to be taken into account that delayed ACKs can be used and ACKs may get lost; therefore, the sender maintains a running estimate of the packet marking ratio and uses this estimate to determine the amount with which to reduce the congestion window when the congestion algorithm decides on a multiplicative decrease. Note that still only one multiplicative decrease per RTT is performed.

Recently, proposals were made to use these new congestion control concepts in the open Internet, where they need to coexist with the traditional congestion control mechanisms. Therefore, (i) the way the network provides feedback needs to be reconsidered [25][27], (ii) a better mechanism to send more accurate ECN feedback than once per RTT is needed [26], and (iii) a new version of TCP (often referred to as TCP Prague) [34], is needed, which relies on this (accurate) ECN feedback to determine the rate at which it can send information from its sender to its receiver.

Figure 13 compares the performance in case a traditional TCP flow (orange curves) competes with an L4S TCP flow (blue curves) over a 5G testbed or over a WiFi access point. It can be seen that in both cases, the latency seen by the L4S TCP flow is much lower than the one seen by the traditional TCP flow, while the throughput of both flows is almost the same, guaranteeing fairness from one flow to the other. Notice also that the L4S TCP flow gets more frequent feedback (in the form of ECN marks) than the traditional TCP flow (in the form of lost packets).

Figure 14 illustrates the difference in RLC buffer evolution for the four traffic classes considered in the case without AQM (treated in deliverables D3.1, D3.2, D5.1 and D5.2) and the case with L4S. It can be seen that, as expected, the RLC buffer occupancy is kept low in the latter case, which may have a drastic effect on the performance of the classification algorithms.

3.4.1.3 *Performance of the classification algorithms*

This detailed performance of the algorithms on the new data set will be presented in deliverable D5.3. Here, we just mention that the performance is poor when the classification algorithms trained on the non-L4S data are used on the L4S data and that when retraining the classification algorithms on the L4S data, the performance is as good as before.

3.4.1.4 *Conclusions*

Using L4S as AQM on the RLC buffer to keep the latency under control has an impact on the performance of the traffic classification algorithms, in the sense that continuing the use of the algorithms trained on non-L4S data when L4S is activated yields a low performance. However, if the algorithms are retrained on data where L4S was activated as AQM, the performance is restored.

Figure 13. Comparison of the performance of traditional and L4S congestion control on the 5G test bed (top) and on WiFi (bottom).

Figure 14. Impact of L4S on the RLC buffer occupancy evolution for the four traffic classes considered (mobile1 transports video, mobile2 web, mobile3 podcast and mobile4 bulk data transfer), (left) without L4S, (right) with L4S.

3.4.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

3.4.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 8. Reliable Distributed Unit (DU) usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	Through this interface, the algorithm discussed in Section 3.4 of this deliverable, in Section 2.3 of D3.2 [2] and in Section 4.3 of D3.1 [1], reports an estimate of the current performance of the classification algorithm. These results may then be used to possibly trigger a re-training of the classifier. Since the classifier is trained (and is to be retrained) on labeled data (as it is a supervised learning technique), the new data needs to be gathered (in a live network) by setting up tests during which traffic of which the nature is known, is sent over the RAN. Based on this newly gathered data, the evolution of the performance (i.e., classification accuracy) must be tracked, and the classifier needs to be retrained if that performance drops too much.
Nio-Nifcm	This interface is not used by the classifier.
Nifm-Nifnis	Besides the standard creation and termination procedures, this interface is used to update the parameters that determine the classifier (e.g., the parameters of the neural network that embodies the classifier) after the classifier is retrained.
Nifcm-Nivi	N/A (This interface is not used by the classifier).
Nio-MLp	Through this interface, the necessary data and triggers are given to retrain the classifier.
Mlo-Ncat	This interface is used to redeploy a retrained classifier.
Nio-MANO	N/A (This interface is not used by the classifier).
Nio-Ext	N/A (This interface is not used by the classifier).

3.4.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We detail how this classifier uses the NIF management procedure discussed in Section 5.1.3 of D2.3 [3].

1. This procedure is initiated if the performance of the classifier (on injected test cases) drops.
2. It first inspects the NIS Catalog for available models and then trains a number of these models with the subset of the new data and assesses the performance of each on another subset of the new data. Finally, it selects the best-performing model.
3. The new model is then activated through the Nio-Ncat interface.

3.4.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 9. Application-aware radio scheduling. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
FR-SLMANO-000	Effective (80%)	The classifier, i.e., the key component in the Application Aware RAN (AAR), operates without human intervention once the labeled data is captured: it is trained supervised learning and stops automatically before it is over-trained, while the interference is operated without any human interaction.
FR-SLMANO-002	Effective (80%)	We have trained and (cross)tested the classifier (which plays a central role in the AAR) on two distinct datasets, i.e., one captured with tail-drop buffers and one captured with L4S activated (see D3.3 and D5.3), the former of which aims at maximizing throughput, while the latter of which respects a strict latency bound. Ideally, the AAR classifier allows fine-tuning the traffic differentiation based on class-specific intents, e.g., low latency for XR and high throughput for bulk downloads.
FR-SLMANO-005	Effective (80%)	It was shown that training the classifier on one data set and testing on another yielded a low performance (see D5.3), indicating that a change in the buffer acceptance mechanism can be easily detected when observing the performance of the traffic classifier.

The status of the above requirements is 80%, rather than 100%, because we trained the classification algorithm with emulated data captured on a testbed. To be more precise, the (video, web, podcast and FTP) sources were real, but the mobile and the air interface over which they connect were emulated. Although it is expected that the performance of the classifier on data captured in a scenario with real mobiles will not differ much, we still want to actually do these experiments to confirm this statement.

3.5 Compute-aware scheduling analytics VNFs

3.5.1 Solution description

In this iteration of the solution, we introduce two main upgrades: first, the scheduling of the analytics procedure is now distributed; second, the scheduling process now also includes the offloading decision itself, as opposed to only specifying the system parameters.

In this study, we tackle the issue of edge-assisted analytics in systems with limited resources by presenting and examining a comprehensive selective offloading framework. The devices carry out their tasks locally and only offload them to cloudlet servers when they anticipate a substantial enhancement in performance. We consider a practical scenario where the gains from offloading and the associated resource costs vary over time. To maximize service performance without prior knowledge of this information, we propose an online optimization algorithm. Our approach utilizes an approximate dual subgradient method in combination with a primal-averaging scheme, and it operates under minimal assumptions regarding system stochasticity. We fully implement the proposed algorithm in a wireless testbed and assess its effectiveness using a cutting-edge image recognition application, demonstrating significant improvements in performance and cost savings.

Next, we present the system model along with the notation.

Figure 15. System model including the local/cloudlet classifiers and predictors. Each device is constrained by its average power budget, and the cloudlet has a limited computation capacity.

The devices establish a connection with the cloudlet using high-capacity cellular or Wi-Fi links, as illustrated in Figure 15. Initially, we assume that there are no restrictions on data transfer. Each device, denoted as " n ," has a power budget of B_n on average, which determines the amount of power it can utilize for transmitting images to the cloudlet. The average power consumption is a critical constraint in such systems due to various factors: limited energy budget of the devices, power consumption limitations imposed by their small size, transmission constraints imposed by protocols, or constraints on the power cost imposed by users seeking this service. Similarly, the cloudlet has an average processing capacity of H cycles per second, which is shared among all devices. When the total workload exceeds the capacity H , the task delay increases rapidly, ultimately resulting in an unresponsive system.

When device n transmits an image to the cloudlet in slot t , it consumes σ_{nt} Watts from the device's power budget. This value can fluctuate across slots due to factors such as varying channel conditions, shadowing effects, interference from other transmissions, etc. The power consumption follows a random process $\{\sigma_{nt}\}_t$. Additionally, each transmitted image s_{nt} requires a certain number of cloudlet processing cycles, denoted as h_{nt} . The processing cycles may vary over time due to factors like different image sizes and can be modeled as a random process $\{h_{nt}\}_t$. Our model is designed to handle general scenarios where the requests, power consumption, and computing costs per request can vary arbitrarily over time and have unknown statistics. The devices aim to involve the cloudlet only when they anticipate a significant improvement in classification precision and have a high level of confidence in this expectation.

3.5.1.1 Formulation

The optimization problem is formulated below in P1. In other words, we aim to find the offload probabilities that correspond to the maximum expected advantage over local computing, subject to local energy budgets B_n and cloudlet processing capacity.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbb{P}_1: \underset{\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{Y}}{\text{maximize}} \quad & \sum_{j=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N w_n^j y_n^j \rho^j \\
 \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{j=1}^M y_n^j \sigma_n^j \rho^j \leq B_n, \quad n \in \mathcal{N}, \\
 & \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N y_n^i h_n^i \rho^i \leq H.
 \end{aligned}$$

To streamline the presentation, we denote the objective and constraints of the previous problem with

$$f(\mathbf{y}) = - \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M y_n^j w_n^j \rho^j,$$

$$g_n(\mathbf{y}) = \sum_{j=1}^M y_n^j \sigma_n^j \rho^j - B_n, \forall n \in \mathcal{N},$$

$$g_{N+1}(\mathbf{y}) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M y_n^j h_n^j \rho^j - H,$$

Note that the above functions are indexed with t for their instantaneous versions instead of the average ones. i.e., w_{nt}^j and ρ_t^j . The same thing applies to the decision variables y_t . We present an algorithm that guarantees the convergence to the solution of P1 with time.

3.5.1.2 Proposed Algorithm & Corresponding Guarantees

The basis of our approach is the application of a dual-ascent algorithm where the iterations are in sync with the system's time slots t . Specifically, in each iteration t , we minimize the formulated Lagrangian.

Algorithm 1: OnAlgo

```

1: Initialization:  $t = 0, \lambda_0 = 0, \forall n, j$ 
2: while True do
3:   for each device  $n \in \mathcal{N}$  do
4:      $y_{nt}^j = 0, \forall j$ 
5:     Receive object  $s_{nt}$ 
6:     Classify objects and obtain  $J_n(s_{nt}), d_n(s_{nt}), \forall s_{nt}$ 
7:     Use classification results on predictor to obtain  $w_{nt}$ 
8:     Observe partial current state  $j_t$  and send it to cloudlet
9:     if  $\lambda_{nt} \sigma_n^j + \mu_t h_n^j < w_n^j$  then
10:       $y_n^j \leftarrow 1$  % Send object to cloudlet
11:    end if
12:    Receive updated distribution  $\rho_t^j$  from the cloudlet
13:     $\lambda_{n,t+1} \leftarrow [\lambda_{nt} + \alpha_t (\sum_{j=1}^M \sigma_n^j \rho_t^j y_n^j - B_n)]^+, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}$ 
14:  end for
15:  Cloudlet: Receive partial system states from devices, and
  send back  $\rho_t^j$ 
16:  Compute tasks received from all devices
17:   $\mu_{t+1} \leftarrow [\mu_t + \alpha_t (\sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M h_n^j \rho_t^j y_n^j - H)]^+$ 
18:  Send  $\mu_{t+1}$  to devices
19:   $t \leftarrow t + 1$ 
20: end while

```

Figure 16. The online task outsourcing algorithm called OnAlgo.

The online task outsourcing algorithm, henceforth called OnAlgo, is based on eq. (7)-(9). The details are presented in Figure 16. When each device n receives an object s_{nt} in slot t , it uses its classifier to predict its class and the predictor to estimate the cloudlet's classification improvement (Steps 5- 7). Then, the device uses its threshold decision rule (Step 9) that compares the expected benefits for state j_t with the outsourcing costs for the device and cloudlet. If the cloudlet is not expected to offer satisfactory gains (or, even worse, has lower accuracy), the devices refrain from offloading their tasks. The devices receive the updated state distribution from the cloudlet (Step 12) and update their local dual variable for the power constraint (Step 13). The cloudlet evaluates the current system state and sends it to devices (step 15). It classifies the received objects and updates its congestion variable (Step 17), also sent to devices.

We prove in the paper [35] that the above-mentioned algorithm produces decision variables $\{y_t\}_t$ that converge to the solution of P_1 . Specifically, we have that for the objective function f and the constraints g , we have the following bounds (in the following Figure 17) that hold for a constant or diminishing a_t (which can make the corresponding upper bounds go to 0 as $T \rightarrow \infty$).

Average performance gap between OnAlgo and the optimal solution.

(a): $\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T f(\mathbf{y}_t) - f(\mathbf{y}^*) \leq C_T + \frac{\sigma_g^2}{2T} \sum_{t=1}^T a_t$

$- \frac{\|\lambda_{T+1}\|^2}{2Ta_T} + \frac{1}{2T} \sum_{t=1}^T \|\lambda_t\|^2 \left(\frac{1}{a_t} - \frac{1}{a_{t-1}} \right)$

Norm of a vector that groups the constraints' violations.

(b): $\left\| \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T g(\mathbf{y}_t) \right\| \leq \frac{\|\lambda_{T+1}\|}{Ta_T} + \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \|\delta_t(\mathbf{y}_t)\|$

$+ \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \|\lambda_t\| \left(\frac{1}{a_{t-1}} - \frac{1}{a_t} \right)$

Figure 17. Average optimality gap and constraint violation of OnAlgo.

The above bounds can be shown to be sub-linear by standard choices of the step size a_t . For example, selecting $a_t = 1/\sqrt{t}$ results on sub-linear performance gaps. Namely, both OnAlgo results in an optimality gap and constraint violation that diminish with time at a rate of $O\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{T}}\right)$.

3.5.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

3.5.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 10. Compute-aware scheduling analytics VNFs usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	OnAlgo reports the current value of the performance gap (the LHS of inequality (a) above), as well as the current performance satisfaction metric (the LHS of inequality (b) above). This information can be used to potentially adjust the hyper-parameters of the online learning (increasing or decreasing a_t) based on which of the two metrics is over- or under-delivering.
Nio-Nifcm	This interface is used to monitor the availability of new (virtualized) compute resources on the edge server, which would necessitate re-initializing OnAlgo.
Nifm-Nifnis	This interface will be used for the standard creation and termination procedures, as well as setting parameters such as the dual variable's initial weights, which indicates sensitivity to constraint violation.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface is used together with the Nio-Nifcm to update the resources associated with the NIF, which in turn will trigger a re-initialization of OnAlgo.
Nio-MLp	N/A. This solution is not an instance of supervised learning algorithms.
Mlo-Ncat	N/A. This solution is not an instance of supervised learning algorithms.
Nio-MANO	N/A (This interface is not used by this solution).
Nio-Ext	N/A (This interface is not used by this solution).

3.5.2.2 Usage of the NIO procedures and elements

The solution presented leverages the NIF management procedure discussed in Section 5.1.3 of D2.3 [3].

1. This procedure is initiated if the performance gap or constraint violations are above a certain set threshold. In such a case, the NIO shall pass new hyperparameter values to the NIF.
2. The NIO executes a NIF optimization operation to alter the update formulas in OnAlgo.
3. NIO acknowledges the completion of the NIF management procedure.

3.5.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 11. Compute-aware scheduling analytics VNFs. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirements	Status	Discussion
FR-CAWRS-002	Successful (100%)	This extension optimizes the radio resource scheduling by learning only whether or not offloading is expected to result in performance gains over local execution with the aim of saving radio resource utilization. At the same time, even when offloading decision is taken, the compute resources of the edge are also optimized to respect capacity and time constraints while fulfilling the offloaded task. Hence, the solution presented here, accompanied by its earlier version in D2.2, fulfills the requirements of joint radio-compute optimization.
NFR-CAWRS-001	Successful (100%)	The proposed algorithm was proved to respect the reconfiguration time set by the user.
NFR-CAWRS-002	Successful (100%)	The proposed algorithm was proved to achieve an asymptotically diminishing performance gap with the optimal radio/computing optimization decisions. Namely, the difference in utility and the norm of the constraint satisfaction vector both diminish to 0 with time. Hence, the algorithm fulfills the bounded distance from the optimal requirement.

4 Multi-timescale edge resource management

In the following, we discuss different types of edge resource management solutions, all of them related to fast-changing aspects of mobile networks. We list AI and data-driven resource orchestration (Sections 4.1 and 0) and multi-timescale slice reservation (Section 4.5). Also, we pay attention to energy-related aspects (Section 4.3) and alternative access network solutions (Section 4.2).

4.1 AI-enhanced edge orchestration

4.1.1 Solution description

This solution was thoroughly discussed in Section 3.1 of D3.2 [2].

4.1.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

Two NIFs are combined to create an AI-enhanced orchestration as an NIS, i.e., Service relocation and Federated Learning Powered Anomaly Detection. If both of these NIFs are available in the catalog, NIO proceeds with NIS *creation*. However, both of these NIFs are still fully capable of running as standalone NISs depending on the scenario and deployment that NIO pursues. During the management procedures, the NIO can decide to change the NIF version that is assigned to a particular NIS for AI-enhanced service relocation, which could happen if the Service relocation NIF is trained on top of the edge computing unit that significantly differs in terms of computing power from the one where the NIF is supposed to be deployed. In that case, if no corresponding instance of NIF Service relocation is available, the NIO could trigger the creation of a new NIF (trained on a corresponding dataset), and then trigger the instantiation of a new NIS that contains this newly created Service relocation NIF.

In Table 12, we show the usage of internal interfaces defined in D2.3 [3] to model interactions between the NIO and the respective NIFs, and NIF and NIF-C managers, towards improving the performance of models running, e.g., within the NIF Service relocation described in Section 3.1 of D3.2 [2].

4.1.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 12. Usage of internal interfaces for AI-enhanced orchestration.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	As the Maestro model reported in D3.2 [2], embedded within the Service relocation NIF, works in parallel with the anomaly detection function (Federated Learning Powered Anomaly Detection NIF), conflicting decisions might occur, and such situations need to be resolved by NIO. In the case Maestro receives a notification about an anomaly on a certain edge node that is selected for service deployment, it may use this interface to trigger conflict resolution or possible retraining of NIFs.
Nio-Nifcm	This interface could be utilized to ensure the corresponding virtualized resources needed for Maestro's smooth operation. At the same time, this interface allows for collecting NIF performance metrics, such as reliability and overall processing time.
Nifm-Nifnis	Similarly, as Service relocation NIF performs enhanced life-cycle management of application services (such as ones for vehicular use cases), the NIF Manager could use this interface to manage the NIF life cycle by, e.g., relocating this NIF from one edge unit to another, depending on the availability of resources that are required for its performance.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface allows NIFs such as Service relocation (performed by Maestro) and Federated Learning Powered Anomaly Detection to interact with the virtualized services running on top of the virtualized network infrastructure in Kubernetes clusters, which are deployed as containerized functions. Thus, the service relocation procedure of underlying vehicular services could be triggered using this interface.
Nio-MLp	By using this interface, NIO may trigger the retraining of Maestro within the Service relocation NIF in case the input data used for training (edge networks infrastructure metrics such as CPU, memory, storage, and power) has significantly changed due to the maintenance that involved installation of new or replacement of the old edge computing nodes.
Mlo-Ncat	This interface could allow the ML pipeline framework to access multiple versions of the Maestro model that are trained using the datasets that correspond to different times during the day and, as such, to select the appropriate model for NIF deployment (Service relocation). Different variants of the model could also be selected depending on the tradeoff between accuracy and computation time.

Nio-MANO	N/A. Maestro and Service relocation NIF are enhancing the MANO operations performed by Kubernetes or Open Source MANO (OSM) orchestrators.
Nio-Ext	Given the increased mobility in vehicular scenarios tackled by Maestro, this interface could be utilized for handling policy management of NIF instances running across multiple edge network domains whose NIFs are orchestrated by different NIOs.

4.1.2.2 *Usage of the NIO procedures and elements*

We detail in this subsection how this solution leverages the NIF management procedure discussed in Section 5.1.3 of D2.3 [58].

1. This procedure is initiated when a re-orchestration trigger is fired, and the requested VNF shall be relocated. In this case, through the NIO, the VNF ecosystem running at a given point in time is moved towards the Maestro NIF.
2. Maestro take a decision on the re-location of the VNF and enforces it through the management interfaces, as explained in Table 13.

4.1.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 13. AI-enhanced edge orchestration. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
FR-MTERM-000	Successful (100%)	Given that in network edge environments, services are deployed in a distributed fashion, the decentralized orchestrators that run on the edge should collaborate with each other and consider the resource consumption across the edges to make optimal decisions on service placement. In particular, AI-enhanced edge orchestration leverages NIFs to improve the decision-making on orchestrating and managing distributed resources and to apply decisions in an automated manner.
FR-MTERM-004 (FR-MTERM-004.01, FR-MTERM-004.02)	Successful (100%)	To make decisions for AI-enhanced edge orchestration systems or to perform model retraining, NIFs are constantly collecting data from various sources. The relevant sources, in this case, are computing nodes (resource consumption), network (latency, bandwidth), and application services running on the edge (data traffic and application-specific metrics). Another type of monitored data considered when making decisions is the power consumption of edge nodes.
FR-MTERM-020	Successful (100%)	In the proposed solution, when the decision made by edge orchestrators affects different network edge domains, the centralized orchestrator needs to coordinate the decisions that different individual edge orchestrators make. Otherwise, edge orchestrators can autonomously make orchestration decisions that should be enforced on the edge service deployments in their respective domains.
FR-MTERM-006	Successful (100%)	The proposed solution for multi-timescale edge resource management leverages the help from NIFs to perform the orchestration of distributed service deployments optimally and in an automated way, thereby improving the quality of decisions and making those decisions in a more educated way by taking into account a comprehensive set of factors, such as consumption of computing and network resources, energy consumption, QoS measured at the client side (e.g., end-to-end latency), mobility of users, etc.
FR-MTERM-007 (FR-MTERM-007.00, FR-MTERM-007.01)	Successful (100%)	This solution performs on-the-fly reconfiguration of edge service deployments, which are represented as chains of VNFs deployed on top of the NFV infrastructure. This reconfiguration means edge service scaling and relocation from one edge to another, which are the operations that have a goal to improve/maintain service quality.

4.2 WLAN performance prediction for spectrum management

4.2.1 Solution description

There are no more updates regarding this solution. The WLAN performance prediction method was already described in Section 5.2 of D3.1 [1], and the link with the architectural requirements was shown in Section 3.1 of D3.2 [2].

4.2.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

In section 3.2.5 of D3.2 [2], we showcased a possible application of the proposed Graph Neural Network Model (GNN) in the context of futuristic Software Defined WLANs (SD-WLAN). In summary, this application can manage the interference between neighboring Access Points (AP) by allocating the appropriate channels that minimize the inter- and intra-WLAN interference and maximize the user throughput. The procedures and interfaces defined in this section are thought in the context of such possible applications.

4.2.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 14. WLAN performance predictor usage of internal interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	The GNN model reports the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). This information can be used by the NIO to monitor the health of the GNN model and trigger possible retraining procedures if needed.
Nio-Nifcm	Future SD-WLANs will implement the appropriate APIs [36] to communicate with the infrastructure. Thanks to these interfaces, NIO can also check the availability of physical resources and modify parameters in each of the NIF-C. An example of this is the Collector block, where all the input data is aggregated and passed to the Pre-Producer block, where the graph-like structure is formed. Then, if required, the input data's velocity can be modified to fulfill constraints in storage capacity.
Nifm-Nifnis	Through this interface, the NIF Manager could change parameters in the WLAN performance predictor. For instance, as we showed in [37], the accuracy of the GNN model is affected by is greater or lower amount, depending on the set of considered features.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface is used, together with the Nio-Nifcm interface, to access the physical resources of the SD-WLAN. These resources can include storage capacity, computing hardware and spectrum.
Nio-MLp	Through this interface, the aggregated data obtained at the collector block can be leveraged to re-train a newer version of the GNN model, in case it is too old, and its accuracy could be compromised, or even training a simpler model (e.g., XGBoost) in case the infrastructure can no longer host the GNN model.
Mlo-Ncat	As shown in [37], multiple models can be trained to solve the performance prediction in WLANs. A trade-off between accuracy and infrastructure availability and capacity should be carried out to select the best-performing model.
Nio-MANO	N/A. In this case, the NIO integrates the functions of MANO.
Nio-Ext	N/A. In the solution, we assume that multiple WLANs are managed by the same entity so its parameters can be easily accessible and changeable.

4.2.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We detail in this subsection how this solution leverages the NIF management procedure discussed in Section 5.1.3 of D2.3 [3]. We assume that all the NIF-Cs are already deployed and that an NIF and NIF-C Manager are in place.

1. The procedure is initiated when the GNN model reports an RMSE that affects the prediction and the performance of the overall application. In this case, the monitoring block from the NIO reports the increase in the RMSE and then, the NIO triggers an update of the model using the Nio-MLp and the Mlo-Ncat interfaces.
2. If there is a newer version of the GNN model that provides lower RMSE or, alternatively, a better model, then the NIO performs model selection.
3. In case there is no alternative model, then the NIO triggers retraining using the Nio-MLp interface.
4. The resulting model is uploaded to the NIF Manager by using the Nio-Nifm interface, acknowledges the upload and deploys the new model in a posterior step.

4.2.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 15. WLAN performance prediction for spectrum management. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
FR-MTERM-004	Successful (100%)	The GNN model continuously monitors the current spectrum state. Depending on this state and the available channels, the GNN will predict the performance of the WLAN in terms of throughput. This can be extremely powerful since the impact of new changes (e.g., bonded channels, acceptance of new users, reconfiguration of neighboring APs) can be evaluated beforehand to avoid a negative effect on the associated users.
FR-MTERM-006	Successful (100%)	In section 3.2.5 of D3.2 [2] and in this section, we showed how the GNN model can be used to support the orchestration of spectrum resources through channel allocation.

4.3 Energy aware edge resource management

4.3.1 Solution description

4.3.1.1 SAVRUS Module

In Section 5.3.2.1 of D3.1 [1] and Section 3.3.3.1 of D3.2 [2], we defined and evaluated SAVRUS, a domain-independent algorithm to uncover noteworthy features/components of VNFs in the Edge. SAVRUS uses an interactive approach that, via Transfer Learned Statistical Sampling, K-nearest neighbors' prediction, Pair-Wise Mann Whitney U test, and Statistical Triple-Wise analysis, and some available measures at hand provides energy consumption (or similar quality attributes) insights of IoT/Edge/Cloud system developers in the range of minutes. Since D3.2, the SAVRUS module has evolved, incorporating several updates [38].

One of these updates has been the study of alternatives to improve the ranking of features based on their constant influence on a specific Quality Attribute (QA), such as energy consumption. Concretely, Inductive Transfer Learning (TL) [39] and the use of a Scoring Function [40]. Inductive TL is a transfer learning technique where the source and target domains and the analysis are similar but not equal. Using TL, instead of purely relying on a single ranking analysis per execution, we can keep track of the frequency of feature detection to create or update the ranking by transferring that information into current analyses instead of purely relying on a single ranking analysis per execution. Additionally, using a Scoring Function, we can build the ranking based on the weights of this function. The score function is the gradient of features' logarithmic likelihood for the confident values of the function. Confident scores allow ordering a set of values and indicate the steepness of the function (i.e., sensitivity to changes) [41].

The SAVRUS algorithm described in D3.1 has been updated to incorporate these new techniques. Concretely, the new version of SAVRUS identifies which features are shared among the worst-performing configuration samples for the QA that are analyzed. For this, it starts by computing the average performance $P(f)$ of configurations with a feature f , and the average performance $P(\text{not}f)$ of configurations without f . Consequently, SAVRUS calculates the influence of a feature such as follows:

$$P\Delta(f) = P(f) - P(\text{not}f)$$

For QAs like runtime or energy consumption, where a higher QA value is underperforming, a $P\Delta(f) > 0$ means that f degrades the QA performance of most of the configurations in the sample set. Further, SAVRUS generates a set with the features shared among the top N underperforming configurations from the sample set. Based on [42]], where a similar approach is used to find the best-performing features, it is experimentally concluded that an $N = 2$ is the most accurate. Elaborating, using only the worst configuration (i.e., $N = 1$) is misleading, as only some of its features are potentially noteworthy. On the other hand, $N \geq 3$ is too constraining, as interesting features may not be in all configurations.

In the new version of the algorithm, SAVRUS also keeps track of the influence scoring, which is the composed likelihood of features affecting a QA based on the accumulated search spaces. We apply TL and follow a similar approach to TL anomaly detection with unsupervised instance selection [43]], but in our case, the ranking scoring is shifted opposite of the anomaly. Anomaly detection involves identifying QA-valued configurations containing noteworthy features or interactions as outliers, meaning that their behavior differs from what was expected. Suppose that in an analysis, we check if that noteworthiness conclusion holds for the k -close configurations in which they are present. If the effect of that feature or interaction in those exact configurations is an outlier, the conclusion does not hold. Hence, the scoring will decrease proportionally to the outlier scoring. Similarly, if the conclusion holds, the ranking scoring increments inversely proportional to the outlier scoring.

4.3.1.2 Local Outlier Factor of k-Closest Neighbors

In the new implementation of the algorithm, we rely on the PHP library Rubix ML 8. Concretely, we make use of its Local Outlier Factor (LOF) method, which measures the local deviation of the density of an unknown sample regarding its kNNs. One can identify the configuration with a substantially lower density than their neighbors by comparing the local density of a configuration to the local densities of its kNNs. As such, LOF only considers the k-neighborhood of an unknown configuration, which enables it to detect anomalies within individual clusters of the measured configuration space. LOF can be executed as unsupervised or as semi-supervised learning. The unsupervised mode finds outliers within itself (i.e., the configuration space). On the other hand, the semi-supervised mode allows comparing the density of a given configuration versus the density of the k-closest neighbors in the measured configuration space. We execute the semisupervised mode as we consider an initial weight of 0 (i.e., not affecting) for each feature and interaction and constantly update the weights. We make use of kNN again, but this time within the LOF method, which is a sequence of:

1. Defining the distance metric, the k hyperparameter, and the algorithm used to compute the NNs. In this version, we keep using the Manhattan distance and $k = 5$ for the same reasons detailed above. Regarding the specific algorithm, Rubyx ML implements the k-d Tree and the Ball Tree algorithms, from which we choose the latter. The reason is that the Ball Tree algorithm works well with various dimensions since the partitioning schema does not rely on a finite number of 1-dimensional axes aligned splits such as with k-d Tree. Ball Tree is a binary spatial tree that partitions the measured configuration space into successively smaller and tighter configuration clusters.

2. Calculating the kth distances of the samples. As mentioned, we chose the Manhattan distance again.

3. Pulling kNN configurations from the measured configuration space that contains the noteworthy feature or interaction to rank. If k-closer configurations do not exist, the scoring of that feature or interaction will not be updated.

4. Calculating each sample's Local Reachability Density (LDR) by estimating the distance at which a sample can be found by its neighboring configurations. LDR is computed as a count of the configurations in the specific kNN set for a sample over its Reachability distance to all the values in the relevant kNN set. Formally, the LDR of a configuration sample X is:

$$LDR(X) = \frac{\#KSamples}{\sum_{Y=KSamples[1]}^{\#KSamples[N]} Reachability(X,Y)}; \text{ where}$$

$$Reachability(X,Y) = \text{Max}\{kDis\ tan\ c\ e(Y), Dis\ tan\ c\ e(X,Y)\}$$

5. Calculating the final LOF value of each sample. It is calculated as the sum of the LRD of all the samples in the respective kNN set, multiplied by the sum of the Reachability distance of all the samples in that kNN set, all divided by the square of the size of that kNN set. Formally, the LDR of configuration sample X :

$$LOF(X) = \frac{\sum_{Y=KSamples[1]}^{\#KSamples[N]} LDR(Y) \cdot \sum_{Z=KSamples[1]}^{\#KSamples[N]} Reachability(X,Z)}{(\#KSamples)^2}$$

6. Defining a threshold to obtain conclusions based on the resulting LOF values. Based on the literature [44], if the measured configuration space is tight, clean, and uniform, LOF values above 1 mean that a feature or interaction performed in the sample is an outlier and cannot be generalized. However, in cases like emergent domains like ours where the measured configuration space is probably sparse, with a varying density, and with local fluctuations in a local cluster, samples are considered outliers with LOF values above 2.

Another clarification is about calculating a k-mean QA value in the kNN step and then calculating the LOF value that again uses kNN. First, they are two different and necessary instances of kNN. Second, their inputs and outputs are other. In the kNN step, the inputs are unmeasured configurations, and the analyses rely on the user-constrained measured configuration space. In the TL step, the inputs are single features and sets of interacting features, and the LOF analyses rely on the features-constrained measured space. On the other hand, the outputs are the k-mean value of unmeasured configurations and a ranking scoring, respectively. The ranking scoring goes from 0 to 1, meaning not affecting and always affecting, respectively. As mentioned, features and valid interactions start with weights of value 0 (i.e., generally not affecting) by default. On each SAVRUS execution, if any of them are detected as statistically noteworthy, the TL step with the LOF method is executed. Then, the weights are updated depending on the respective LOF values. If the LOF value of a feature X is above the anomaly threshold, 2 in our case, it is normalized and subtracted from its scoring weight w_X as $w_X \leftarrow w_X - \frac{LOF(X)}{100}$. On the other hand, if the LOF

value is below the threshold, it is added as $wX += \frac{LOF(X)}{100}$. The weights cannot decrease/increase more than 0/1, respectively. Finally, features and interactions are ordered from 1 to 0, creating the noteworthiness ranking of features and interactions affecting a specific QA.

These changes on the algorithm have been performed to reduce the *Curse of Dimensionality* of kNN and the *Negative Transfer* of transfer learning, two possible limitations of SAVRUS. If the measured space size predominantly grows, the probability of needing the kNN step is proportionally reduced, and thus, SAVRUS could theoretically suffer from the *Curse of Dimensionality*. Variability models in the Clafar language are defined as variability trees; thereupon, the full dimension that SAVRUS analysis could have is somewhere between the maximum depth of the tree plus the number of grouped features if mandatory or disjunction cardinalities are defined. As a worst-case scenario, we could calculate the dimensionality of Linux 2.6.33.3, one of the colossal systems with a configuration space of $\sim 3.90 \times 10^{1672}$. Its maximum dimensionality is ~ 192 [45]. However, that maximum dimensionality is unlikely to arise in every analysis as the average depth of the branches is 2.7, and the total number of features is 6467. Moreover, since SAVRUS accepts feature constraints from the user, this exponentially reduces the configuration space size and, consequently, the probability of larger dimensionalities. Additionally, we can further discard this curse from using the TL with the LOF step, as the measured configuration size is reduced further to the configurations comprising a specific feature, or set of interacting features, detected as noteworthy.

On the other hand, TL could suffer from another issue, which is the Negative Transfer. The definition of negative transfer is still under debate and is based on the algorithms, domain divergence and target data of the specific study [46]. Based on that, negative transfer in SAVRUS could arise if an extended sequence of past executions were based on a cluster of the configuration search space that behaves very differently from the ones in the current analyses. This would cause the resulting rankings to be shifted due to inaccurate scoring weights. However, it does not affect the detection of noteworthy features and interactions but their order (i.e., likelihood) in the ranking. Additionally, its probability is low, as that situation requires analyzing one cluster many times and then analyzing a cluster that performs very differently only once. A new sequence of analyses will properly readjust the scoring weights. This behavior is expected from any TL approach in the early stages of learning a new cluster, and with experience, they correct for these effects.

Finally, it has been empirically demonstrated that SAVRUS generates meaningful results sufficiently fast by analyzing two aspects of our prototype: (1) *SAVRUS validity*. We have analyzed how reliable SAVRUS is concerning coverage and accuracy to identify feature influences based on incompletely measured spaces and (2) *SAVRUS scalability*. We have analyzed the relationship between the number of features, configurations and samples and SAVRUS analysis runtime. The main results, detailed in [38], are as follows:

4.3.1.3 Validity Results

SAVRUS generates a correct ranking of noteworthy features and interactions 80% of the time for every incompletely measured model. This accuracy is inversely proportional to the space size and the number of samples. Statistical Recursive Search (SRS) is generally more accurate than Diversified Distance-based Sampling (DDbS), even with lower coverage. On the other hand, DDbS is comparatively faster, especially for larger spaces. Hence, the results are reasonably accurate without exploiting domain knowledge.

4.3.1.4 Scalability Results

SAVRUS implementation presents an initial analysis runtime of ~ 1 min, taking less than 3 min for comprehensible cases and scenarios, and with a worst-case of ~ 7 min. We have empirically demonstrated that it has a linear relationship with the number and complexity of the samples, getting smoother based on how large the sample set is. Finally, the main bottlenecks are the database and the solver. Hence, it provides linear scalability with reasonable base analysis times.

4.3.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

4.3.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 16. SAVRUS usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	SAVRUS reports a ranking of interacting features through this interface, information managed by the Knowledge Management component and that could cause a re-training of the current system. Due to the nature of the ranking, it can cover any set of NIFs heavily affecting the energy consumption of the system.

Nio-Nifcm	SAVRUS reports a ranking of interacting features through this interface, information managed by the Knowledge Management component and that could cause a re-orchestration of the current system components. Due to the nature of the ranking, it can cover any set of hardware and software components heavily affecting the energy consumption of the system.
Nifm-Nifnis	Energy readings and information on the change of components collected in this interface are used to update SAVRUS models.
Nifcm-Nivi	SAVRUS reports can influence the specific hardware allocations for an NIF.
Nio-MLp	N/A (SAVRUS does not require training)
Mlo-Ncat	N/A (SAVRUS does not require training)
Nio-MANO	SAVRUS information can issue a re-orchestration request to the vRAN system in case of insufficient energy power and energy cuts.
Nio-Ext	Through this interface, SAVRUS models can be updated by external orchestrators for information exchange and viceversa.

4.3.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We detail in this subsection how this solution leverages the NIF management procedure discussed in Section 5.1.3 of D2.3 [58].

3. This procedure is initiated if an energy shortcut is detected. Hence, through the NIO, it decides to request an updated SAVRUS ranking to re-orchestrate some components.
4. By matching the SAVRUS ranking with the NIS Catalog, the system can be updated by switching to a more energy-efficient alternative (e.g., compressing data before transmitting).

4.3.3 Requirement satisfaction

Most of the requirements related to this share of the work are considered 100% complete or mostly completed, as reported below. Regarding the *Global Energy-aware VNF placement* (FR-EAWVNF-000) we have implemented the SAVRUS algorithm that works with unknown-domain (in this case, VNFs for edge-based mobile networks) to identify and rank the main network features and their interactions by how much they affect the final energy consumption with a 95% confidence (D3.1 [1], Section 5.3.2.1, D3.2 [2], Section 3.3.3, and journal [47]). Regarding the *Energy Footprint of VNFs* (FR-EAWVNF-001.01), we calculate an energy consumption model of VNFs in terms of the amount of data transmitted (sent and received) according to the node in which VNFs are deployed. Regarding the *Optimal Placement of VNFs* (FR-EAWVNF-002), we measure and consider the excessive use of additional resources by a certain VNF, strongly impacting the decision of, for example, migrating it to another location. Regarding the *Impact of Hardware Resources* (FR-SLMANO-002), we designed a categorical approach for modeling and reasoning real-world systems pretending to cover a variety of properties (i.e., hardware and software), quality attributes and functions commonly found in systems with VNFs.

Table 17. Energy-aware edge resource management. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
FR-EAWVNF-000	Effective (90%)	In order to meet the goal of energy efficiency, we have to identify the list of elements that strongly affect energy consumption in the edge context. We have implemented the SAVRUS algorithm that works with unknown-domain (in this case, VNFs foredge-based mobile networks) to identify and rank the main network features and their interactions by how much they affect the final energy consumption (D3.1 [1], Section 5.3.2.1, D3.2 [2], Section 3.3.3, and journal [47][48])). We evaluated the SAVRUS strategy with experiments that provide completely measured models by properly degrading the completely measured spaces to represent incomplete measures space, which are the measures spaces under SAVRUS works [47][48]. Regarding the construct validity of the data set, the degradation procedure was automatic and random and was independently applied to the original spaces several times. Consequently, we analyzed the same space many times but degraded it differently to minimize the collateral effects that the degradation procedure could have on the results. There is a risk to the internal validity since the

		selected sampling and learning methods may not be the best choice for all systems. To mitigate this risk, we did not only validate SAVRUS outputs but individually reviewed each strategy component to avoid hidden errors. We repeated the analysis and presented average metrics to reduce a possible bias. Also, SAVRUS comprises a normality test within the process with a 95% confidence. The functionality of SAVRUS is 100% developed. We indicated a status of 90% for this requirement mainly because of the risks described for construct validity and internal validity.
FR-EAVNF-001.01	Successful (100%)	In the energy footprint calculation, we need to consider that some VNFs will produce some data that might need to be transmitted to other devices. We know that the transmission power, the payload and the transmission rate should be considered, along with other terms. In our energy-aware placement solution (see D4.2), the energy model explicitly includes the energy cost of data communication calculated in the amount of bytes sent and received along with other terms. In the autoscaling and placement solution (see D4.2), the energy consumption model calculates the energy footprint of VNFs in terms of the amount of data transmitted (sent and received) according to the node in which VNFs are deployed.
FR-EAVNF-002	Successful (100%)	Measuring the hardware resources usage of VNFs and their energy footprint provides extra information to accurately estimate the overall energy footprint of a VNF. We are seeking to find additional factors to the energy consumption formula to calculate, more precisely, the network energy footprint. Although the DAEMON approach does not need absolute values of energy consumption, we need to find out if there are certain situations where the excessive use of additional resources by a certain VNF strongly impacts the decision of, for example, migrating it to another location. Our solution (see D4.2) monitors the impact of hardware resources of VNFs in the estimation of energy consumption. The solution also considers the computation, communication, and storage resources as part of the placement algorithm.
FR-SLMANO-002.00	Effective (85%)	The CQL framework supports advanced optimization by supporting multi-objective combinations of quality attributes, such as latency and energy consumption. In the evaluation of the CQL framework and to control randomness, we repeated the experiments 97 times and averaged the results for a confidence level of 95% with a 10% margin of error. An external threat to the validity is that not all the evaluated systems are NFVs, but well-known models with registered complex quality measurements are rare in the SDN literature. Consequently, by choosing the real-world systems selected in the evaluation, we pretended to cover a variety of properties, quality attributes and functions commonly found in VNF cases. Nonetheless, we are aware that they do not cover every possible casuistic individually. Moreover, while one could claim that larger systems should be tested, we should mention that larger spaces are very rare for VNF orchestrators. The problem in SDN systems is the complexity of the reasoning and not the size of it. Testing our algorithms with only one Category Theory reasoner could be another threat. The problem is that Category Theory tools are rare due to the intrinsic abstraction and knowledge requirement. The functionality of the CQL framework is 100% developed. We indicated a status of 85% for this requirement mainly because of the risks described in the evaluation of the approach.

4.4 Data-driven resource orchestration

4.4.1 Solution description

In this section, we present the latest status of our work on data-driven resource orchestration. We described the problem that we aimed to solve in D3.1 [1], Section 5.4, and provided an update in D3.2 [2], Section 3.4. Furthermore, in D5.2 [11], Section 4.4.4 (Activity 13), we presented the results of the pilot we have done together with one of Telefonica's operators. Our results show that, as operators prepare to deploy 5G SA solutions, there is a need to accommodate a fine-granular approach in responding to the demand coming from devices deployed globally. Our effort is focused on updating our processing pipeline for integrating 5GC-specific data feeds that the operator presently runs in the testbed.

4.4.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

4.4.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 18. Data-driven resource orchestration usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	The solution in this section leverages this interface to receive the monitoring information towards the clustering module.
Nio-Nifcm	Our solution reports a set of clusters that can help the operator better understand the demand within their network (coming directly from the population of connected devices), information managed by the Knowledge Management component and that could cause a re-orchestration of the current system components.
Nifm-Nifnis	Updates in the main data features are necessary to map devices to a potential cluster that captures their behavior.
Nifcm-Nivi	The results from the data-driven analysis can influence the decision of the operator in terms of slice creation and resource allocation.
Nio-MLp	Our approach requires updating the clustering approach on the device population (or sub-segments of it) in order to generate informed decisions in terms of resource orchestration in the network.
Mlo-Ncat	The model will map a device to a cluster, which is periodically re-defined after re-training.
Nio-MANO	The information from the approach might help the operator to trigger, for example, informed re-orchestration requests to move the UPF closer to the location of the end-user.
Nio-Ext	This interface is not used by the NI since the output is not a direct decision but an insight on network demand that can be used by the operations teams.

4.4.2.2 Usage of the NIO procedures and elements

We detail in this subsection how this solution leverages the NIF management procedures discussed in D2.3 [3].

The pipeline is triggered by a network engineer looking to understand, to a more granular degree, the demand in terms of network resources from devices connected to its radio access network. Oftentimes, these devices are not only native devices of the operator, but they also include inbound roaming devices from foreign operators (both national and international).

The pipeline generates profiles corresponding to the (expected) network demand of certain clusters, which the operator can then use to make informed decisions about their own resources' allocation. Whenever there is a poor cluster profile inference, the pipeline is re-started. In this case, the monitoring block from the NIO reports poor matching for specific devices, and the NIO triggers the update of the clustering scheme.

4.4.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 19. Data-driven resource orchestration. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
FR-MTERM-000	Successful (100%)	Our approach aims to leverage the 5G Control and User Plane Separation (CUPS) to explore the best location of the UPF for specific groups of devices that rely on the core network of the network we analyze but rent different radio resources across the world.

FR-MTERM-004	Successful (95%)	Our solution builds into the big data platform of a real-world operator to generate different analytics and device-level features, which we then use to cluster the devices based on their network requirements. We run this analysis as multiple time scales (1h interval, 4h interval, 24h interval). We maintain our solution to further adapt to new incoming data feeds, such as the ones from the 5G Core (5GC).
FR-MTERM-021	Effective (90%)	Our solution provides the resulting clusters of devices to the Network Intelligence Orchestrator, which can then run the per-device classification and allocate resources to the different devices. Though we have provided an initial integration of this logic within the operator's big data platform, we are maintaining this pipeline to accommodate the recent deployment of the 5G Core in production. The clusters of resources demand change with the evolution of the customer base of the Mobile Network Operator (MNO), requiring periodic updates to the pipeline.

4.5 Multi-timescale network slice reservation

4.5.1 Solution description

We examine the issue of fairness in the context of dynamic resource allocation using the α -fairness principle. In this problem, we identify two distinct fairness objectives that naturally arise: the well-established slot-fairness objective, which aims to ensure fairness at each individual timeslot, and the relatively unexplored horizon-fairness objective, which aims to ensure fairness across utilities accumulated over a specific time span (see Figure 18). We argue that horizon-fairness can be achieved at a lower cost in terms of social welfare. This horizon fairness is investigated using “regret” as a performance metric.

Figure 18: The different ways fairness can be enforced in a time-slotted dynamic system. The decision maker can either consider the α -fairness objective F_α at every timeslot (slot-fairness) or at the end of the time horizon T (horizon-fairness).

4.5.1.1 System Model and Problem Formulation

We consider a system that serves a set of agents, where a controller selects at each time slot t a resource allocation profile x_t based on the utilities achieved by the agents up to $t - 1$. We denote the utility function, revealed at each time step after fixing the allocation profile, by u_t . The α -fairness function is denoted with F_α . The utilities at each time step are allowed to arbitrarily change (even in adversarial fashion), and recall that the controller does not know the utility function when deciding the resource allocation profile. We define next the performance metric (fairness regret of an allocation policy \mathcal{A} under an α fairness function F).

$$\mathfrak{R}_T(F_\alpha, \mathcal{A}) \triangleq \sup_{\{u_t\}_{t=1}^T \in \mathcal{U}^T} \left\{ \max_{x \in \mathcal{X}} F_\alpha \left(\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} u_t(x) \right) - F_\alpha \left(\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} u_t(x_t) \right) \right\}.$$

In other words, the regret measures the maximum discrepancy in α -Fairness values of the time-averaged utilities of the allocation profiles. If a policy achieves a sub-linear regret, if a policy's regret goes to 0 value after T time steps, it means that the policy ensures an α -fair allocation across the time horizon T . As detailed in the paper, we show that it is impossible to achieve such a diminishing regret for a general unconstrained environment (unconstrained adversary). Then, we identify two restrictions on the environment under which it is possible to design policies with diminishing regret.

4.5.1.2 Algorithm and Results

We prove in [58] that at least one of the following is necessary to have a vanishing regret. While we focus here on intuitive high-level description, we refer the reader to the paper for the formal presentation.

- Sub-linear budgeted severity: The budgeted severity bounds the total amount of perturbations of the time-averaged utility. When budgeted severity = 0, the adversary is only able to select a fixed function, otherwise, the adversary is able to select time-varying utilities while keeping the total deviation no more than a specific budget. Moreover, the adversary is allowed to pick opportunely the timeslots to maximize performance degradation for the controller. This model captures realistic scenarios where the utilities incurred at different timeslots are predictable but can be perturbed for some fraction of the timeslots.
- Sub-linear partitioned severity: The partitioned severity captures the maximum perturbation that the adversary can exert during any sub-interval within T (i.e., the deviation it can cancel).

Under the above conditions, we propose the Online Horizon Fair (OHF) policy. The OHF policy employs a novel learning approach that operates concurrently and in a synchronized fashion in a primal and a dual (conjugate) space. Intuitively, OHF learns the weighted time-varying utilities in a primal space and learns the weights accounting for the global fairness metric in some dual space. To achieve this, we develop novel techniques through a convex conjugate approach.

The below box displays our algorithm and define/explain the notation in the adjacent pseudo-code.

Algorithm 1 OHF policy

Require: $\mathcal{X}, \alpha \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}, [u_{\star, \min}, u_{\star, \max}]$

- 1: $\Theta \leftarrow [-1/u_{\star, \min}^\alpha, -1/u_{\star, \max}^\alpha]^I$ ▷ Initialize the dual (conjugate) subspace
- 2: $\mathbf{x}_1 \in \mathcal{X}; \boldsymbol{\theta}_1 \in \Theta$; ▷ Initialize allocation \mathbf{x}_1 and dual decision $\boldsymbol{\theta}_1$
- 3: **for** $t \in \mathcal{T}$ **do**
- 4: Reveal $\Psi_{t, \alpha}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) = (-F_\alpha)^\star(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t) - \boldsymbol{\theta}_t \cdot \mathbf{u}_t(\mathbf{x}_t)$ ▷ Incur reward $\Psi_{t, \alpha}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t, \mathbf{x}_t)$ and loss $\Psi_{t, \alpha}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t, \mathbf{x}_t)$
- 5: $\mathbf{g}_{\mathcal{X}, t} \in \partial_{\mathbf{x}} \Psi_{t, \alpha}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} \theta_{t, i} \partial_{\mathbf{x}} u_{t, i}$ ▷ Compute supergradient $\mathbf{g}_{\mathcal{X}, t}$ at \mathbf{x}_t of reward $\Psi_{t, \alpha}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t, \cdot)$
- 6: $\mathbf{g}_{\Theta, t} = \nabla_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \Psi_{t, \alpha}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) = \left((-\theta_{t, i})^{-1/\alpha} - \mathbf{u}_t(\mathbf{x}_t) \right)_{i \in \mathcal{I}}$ ▷ Compute gradient $\mathbf{g}_{\Theta, t}$ at $\boldsymbol{\theta}_t$ of loss $\Psi_{t, \alpha}(\cdot, \mathbf{x}_t)$
- 7: $\eta_{\mathcal{X}, t} = \text{diam}(\mathcal{X}) / \sqrt{\sum_{s=1}^t \|\mathbf{g}_{\mathcal{X}, s}\|_2^2}; \eta_{\Theta, t} = \alpha u_{\min}^{-1-1/\alpha} / t$ ▷ Compute adaptive learning rates
- 8: $\mathbf{x}_{t+1} = \Pi_{\mathcal{X}}(\mathbf{x}_t + \eta_{\mathcal{X}, t} \mathbf{g}_{\mathcal{X}, t}); \boldsymbol{\theta}_{t+1} = \Pi_{\Theta}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_t - \eta_{\Theta, t} \mathbf{g}_{\Theta, t})$ ▷ Compute a new allocation and dual decision

Figure 19. OHF policy.

OHF can be looked at as a saddle point optimization with gradient ascent (in the primal space) and gradient descent (in the dual space) steps. The policy uses its input to initialize the dual (conjugate) subspace, an initial allocation and a dual decision (lines 1–2 in Figure 19). At a given timeslot $t \in T$, the allocation is selected; then a vector-valued utility is revealed and, in turn, (line 4 in Figure 19). The gradients are computed (lines 5–6 in Figure 19). The policy then finally performs an adaptation of its state variables via a descent step in the dual space and an ascent step in the primal space through Online Gradient Descent (OGD) and Online Gradient Ascent (OGA) policies, respectively (line 8 in Figure 19). The main result is that the regret of the allocation decisions by the OHF policy decays with time. Namely, $R_T(F_\alpha, A) \leq O(\frac{1}{\sqrt{T}})$, i.e., OHF is guaranteed to produce α -fair allocations as time increases.

4.5.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

4.5.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 20. Multi-timescale network slice reservation usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	OnAlgo reports the current fairness gap to the α -fair resource/slice allocation profile.
Nio-Nifcm	This interface is used to monitor the availability of new (virtualized) compute resources, which would necessitate re-initializing the OHF algorithm.
Nifm-Nifnis	This interface will be used for the standard creation and termination procedures, as well as setting the fairness parameter α , which would impact the allocation decisions by OHF.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface is used together with the Nio-Nifcm to update the resources associated with the NIF, which in turn will trigger a re-initialization of OHF.
Nio-MLp	N/A. This solution is not an instance of supervised learning algorithms.
Mlo-Ncat	N/A. This solution is not an instance of supervised learning algorithms.
Nio-MANO	N/A (This interface is not used).
Nio-Ext	N/A (This interface is not used).

4.5.2.2 Usage of the NIO procedures and elements

This is an online algorithm that achieves fairness at two different time scales between general networking entities. The main NIF management procedures needed here are the creation and termination. Discussion in Section 5.1.1 and 5.1.4 of D2.3 [3]. For the creation procedure:

1. This procedure is initiated when new resources are available and it is desired that the NIO allocates them according to some α -fairness criteria.
2. The NIO determines the required creation parameters, which are the resolution (duration) of the time slot t , as well as the horizon value T .

For the termination, the OHF algorithm does not have interdependency with other NIF/NIS discussed here. Hence, it can be terminated.

4.5.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 21. Multi-timescale fairness in networks. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
FR-MTERM-000	Successful (100%)	The suggested algorithm is fully automated and guarantees optimal α -fair allocations for the entire time horizon T .
FR-MTERM-020	Successful (100%)	The coordination between the two time scales is available since the utilities obtained at each time step t contribute to adjusting the future decisions (update formulas in line 8 in Alg. OHF) of the OHF policy such that, across the entire horizon T , the result $R_T(F_\alpha, A) \leq O(\frac{1}{\sqrt{T}})$ holds.

5 Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS) control

5.1 RISMA

5.1.1 Solution description

In D3.1 [1], Section 6, we described a problem that aimed at optimizing jointly the precoding strategy of a Base Station (BS) and the passive beamforming configuration of a RIS to minimize the sum mean squared error, which is known to relate to the sum rate performance. As a reminder, our problem can be formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{W}}{\text{minimize}} && \sum_k \sum_j |\mathbf{v}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{w}_j|^2 - 2 \sum_k \text{Re}\{\mathbf{v}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{w}_k\} \\ & \text{subject to} && |v_i|^2 \leq 1, \quad i = 1, \dots, N; \\ & && v_{N+1} = 1; \\ & && \|\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 \leq P; \end{aligned}$$

Equation 1. RIS problem formulation.

where \mathbf{W} is the transmitter's precoding configuration, and \mathbf{v} is the RIS configuration; $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \text{diag}(\mathbf{h}_k^H) \mathbf{G} \\ \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{(N+1) \times M}$, with \mathbf{h}_k^H being the Hermitian transpose of the channel between the RIS and user k and $\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H$ being the channel between the BS and user k , and P is the power budget of the BS. We refer the reader to D3.1 for further details and a description of the notation.

Given this problem, D3.2 [2] introduced, in Section 4, a solution for the case of a single UE, i.e., $K=1$. In the remainder of this section, we provide a solution for the general case when $K \geq 1$.

Equation 1 which is not jointly convex in \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{W} whereas, differently than prior work, is convex in the two optimization variables separately. We can thus solve Equation 1 efficiently via alternating optimization. If \mathbf{W} is fixed, then Equation 1 (P_SMSE) reduces as follows

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\mathbf{v}}{\text{minimize}} && \sum_k \|\mathbf{v}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{W}\|^2 - 2 \sum_k \text{Re}\{\mathbf{v}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{w}_k\} \\ & \text{subject to} && |v_i|^2 \leq 1 \quad i = 1, \dots, N; \\ & && v_{N+1} = 1. \end{aligned}$$

which admits the following solution

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{v} &= \left(\sum_k \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{W} \mathbf{W}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k^H + \text{Diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) \right)^{-1} \left(\sum_k \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{w}_k - v \mathbf{e}_{N+1} \right) \\ \mathbf{v} &= \left(\sum_k \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{W} \mathbf{W}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k^H + \text{Diag}(\boldsymbol{\mu}) \right)^{-1} \\ &\quad \times \left(\sum_k \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{w}_k - v \mathbf{e}_{N+1} \right), \end{aligned}$$

where \mathbf{e}_{N+1} is the $(N+1)$ -th column of the identity matrix of size $N+1$ and $\boldsymbol{\mu} \geq \mathbf{0}$ is a vector of non-negative variables to be determined in the following way

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_i &= 0 \text{ and } |v_i|^2 \leq 1, \\ \mu_i &\geq 0 \text{ and } |v_i|^2 = 1, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, N. \end{aligned}$$

To alleviate the task of finding $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ in Eq. we set $\boldsymbol{\mu} = \sigma_n^2 \mathbf{1}$. Let

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathbf{v}} &= \left(\sum_k \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{W} \mathbf{W}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k^H + \sigma_n^2 \mathbf{I}_{N+1} \right)^{-1} \\ &\quad \times \left(\sum_k \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{w}_k - v \mathbf{e}_{N+1} \right) \end{aligned}$$

where \mathbf{I}_{N+1} is the identity matrix of size $N+1$. Hence, we have that

$$\mathbf{v} = \frac{\bar{\mathbf{v}}}{\|\bar{\mathbf{v}}\|}.$$

Lastly, v is found by letting $v_{N+1} = 1$ as

$$v = \frac{\mathbf{e}_{N+1}^T \mathbf{B} \mathbf{z} - 1}{\mathbf{e}_{N+1}^T \mathbf{B} \mathbf{e}_{N+1}}.$$

where

$$\mathbf{B} = \left(\sum_k \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{W} \mathbf{W}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k^H + \sigma_n^2 \mathbf{I}_{N+1} \right)^{-1},$$

$\mathbf{z} = \sum_k \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{w}_k$ and \mathbf{e}_{N+1} is the $(N+1)$ -th column of the identity matrix of size $N+1$.

The solution of the above problem] is analytically derived in [49]. When \mathbf{v} is fixed, the above reduces to:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\mathbf{W}}{\text{minimize}} && \sum_k \|\bar{\mathbf{h}}_k^H \mathbf{W}\|^2 - 2 \sum_k \text{Re}\{\bar{\mathbf{h}}_k^H \mathbf{W} \mathbf{e}_k\} \\ & \text{subject to} && \|\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 \leq P; \end{aligned}$$

where we define $\bar{\mathbf{h}}_k \triangleq \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k^H \mathbf{v}$ and \mathbf{e}_k is the k -th column of the identity matrix of size K . Again, given the convexity of the above problem, the KKT conditions are necessary and sufficient for the solution of the problem and yield the following

$$\mathbf{W} = (\bar{\mathbf{H}} \bar{\mathbf{H}}^H + \mu \mathbf{I}_M)^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{H}},$$

with $\bar{\mathbf{H}} = [\bar{\mathbf{h}}_1, \dots, \bar{\mathbf{h}}_K]$ and $\mu \geq 0$ such that $\|\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 = P$ is satisfied². We then set $\mu = \frac{K\sigma_n^2}{P}$, which is proven to maximize the UEs SINRs in the limit of large K while proving to be tight for even small values of K . Hence, we obtain the following empirical closed-form expression for the precoding matrix \mathbf{W}

$$\mathbf{W} = \sqrt{P} \frac{\bar{\mathbf{W}}}{\|\bar{\mathbf{W}}\|_F}$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{W}} = (\bar{\mathbf{H}} \bar{\mathbf{H}}^H + \frac{K\sigma_n^2}{P} \mathbf{I}_M)^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{H}}$.

We derive this equation in [49] by solving the KKT conditions.

Due to the convex nature of both problems, we propose an efficient algorithm, namely RISMA, which alternates the optimization of both the precoding strategy at the BS \mathbf{W} and the RIS setting parameters in \mathbf{v} . Thanks to the convex nature of the two partial problems for which we have found an optimal solution, the proposed algorithm is formally described in Figure 20.

Algorithm 1 RISMA: RIS-aided Multiuser Alternating optimization

- 1: Initialize $\mathbf{W}^{(0)}$, $\text{SMSE}^{(0)}$ and ϵ
 - 2: $n \leftarrow 1$
 - 3: **while** $|(\text{SMSE}^{(n)} - \text{SMSE}^{(n-1)})/\text{SMSE}^{(n)}| > \epsilon$ **do**
 - 4: $\mu = \sigma_n^2 \mathbf{1}$
 - 5: $\nu \leftarrow \text{Force } v_{N+1}^{(n)} = 1$
 - 6:
$$\bar{\mathbf{v}} = \left(\sum_k \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{W} \mathbf{W}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k^H + \text{Diag}(\mu) \right)^{-1} \left(\sum_k \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{w}_k - \nu \mathbf{e}_{N+1} \right)$$
 - 7:
$$\mathbf{v}^{(n)} = \frac{\bar{\mathbf{v}}}{\|\bar{\mathbf{v}}\|}$$
 - 8: $\bar{\mathbf{H}} = [\bar{\mathbf{H}}_1^H \mathbf{v}^{(n)}, \dots, \bar{\mathbf{H}}_K^H \mathbf{v}^{(n)}]$
 - 9:
$$\mu = \frac{K\sigma_n^2}{P}$$
 - 10: $\bar{\mathbf{W}} = (\bar{\mathbf{H}} \bar{\mathbf{H}}^H + \mu \mathbf{I}_M)^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{H}}$
 - 11:
$$\mathbf{W}^{(n)} = \sqrt{P} \frac{\bar{\mathbf{W}}}{\|\bar{\mathbf{W}}\|_F}$$
 - 12:
$$\text{SMSE}^{(n)} = \sum_k \sum_j |(\mathbf{v}^{(n)})^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{w}_j^{(n)}|^2 - 2 \sum_k \text{Re}\{(\mathbf{v}^{(n)})^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{w}_k^{(n)}\} + K(1 + \sigma_n^2)$$
 - 13: **end while**
 - 14: $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}^{(n)}$
 - 15: $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}^{(n)}$
-

Figure 20: RISMA: RIS-aided Multi-user Alternating Optimization.

² In order to determine μ we can apply a bisection method.

A practical approximation of this algorithm, compatible with low-resolution RIS, is presented in [49]. A performance evaluation will be presented in D5.3.

5.1.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

5.1.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 22. RISMA usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	Through this interface, the algorithm discussed in Section 5.1 reports the current statistics on channel state information.
Nio-Nifcm	This interface is used to orchestrate the algorithm in the RIS controller.
Nifm-Nifnis	Besides the standard creation and termination procedures, this interface is used to configure certain parameters of RISMA, such as the number of UEs.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface is used to handle the lifecycle management of the NIF.
Nio-MLp	N/A (this solution does not require training)
Mlo-Ncat	N/A (this solution does not require training)
Nio-MANO	With this interface, the NIO can (re-)orchestrate computing resources in the RIS controller to run RISMA.
Nio-Ext	This interface communicates with the RIS controller.

5.1.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We detail in this subsection how this solution leverages the NIF management procedure discussed in Section 5.1.3 of D2.3 [3].

3. This procedure is initiated if the computing time of the algorithm is above a certain threshold (e.g., 100 ms). In such a case, via the NIO, it shall allocate more computing resources to the NIF.
4. The NIO executes a NIF scaling operation to allocate more computing resources to accelerate RISMA.
5. NIO acknowledges the completion of the NIF management procedure.
6. The O-DU system Acknowledges the new parameters.

5.1.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 23. RISMA. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
FR-RIS-000	Successful (100%)	This NI Functionality jointly optimizes the precoding configuration of a base station in conventional Radio Access Networks and the passive beamforming parameters of a Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS). Risks were low. There was an initial risk that a RIS prototype may not have been available for experimentation. In such a case analytical data would have been used. But the risk has not been materialized.
FR-RIS-001	Successful (100%)	This NI Functionality jointly optimizes the precoding configuration of a base station in conventional Radio Access Networks and the passive beamforming parameters of a Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS). Risks were low.
FR-RIS-002	Successful (100%)	This NI Functionality uses Channel State Information (CSI) in a BS to do its optimization. Since the optimization is done in the BS itself, the initial risk of not receiving data in a timely manner has not materialized.
FR-RIS-003	Successful (100%)	The extensions described above extend our initial work presented in D3.2 to support multiple users. Hence, the risk associated with this requirement has not been materialized.
FR-RIS-004	Successful (100%)	Our RIS prototype, which was introduced in D5.2, is modular and enables a variable number of reflective cells. Its empirical characterization will be presented in D5.3. Hence, this risk has not been materialized.

6 In-backhaul learning

As described in Section 5.1 of D3.2 [2], we bring NI into the Transport level of the edge-to-core continuum to meet the sub-millisecond latency requirement of B5G services. To this end, we map ML algorithms into the PISA architecture of P4-programmable switches, unlocking the possibility to run inference fully into the user plane at line rate.

6.1 Random Forest models in programmable switches

Due to the resource constraints and limited support for mathematical operations of such network devices, we use random forest models that i) fit the architecture better and ii) perform as well as more complex neural network models. In D3.2, we presented our solution Flowrest [58], which exploits features calculated over multiple packets of the same flow to early classify flows of packets. In D5.2 [11], we presented experimental results showing how Flowrest has better classification performances than a packet-level state-of-the-art solution that we used as a benchmark. The performance advantage comes with a cost in terms of resource usage, as Flowrest needs more logic to allow flow management and flow-level feature handling.

Following the requirement about resource prudence for in-backhaul inference, reported in D2.2 [58], we designed a packet-level solution that consumes fewer resources of the switch and yet shows good classification scores. Such a solution, which we call Henna [58], takes advantage of the hierarchical classification paradigm by decomposing a complex classification task into multiple smaller ones.

Even though Flowrest is the most effective solution in terms of performance, it needs to observe a specific number n of packets for each flow to make the prediction. Even if n is small (equal to 3 packets for most of the use cases analyzed), this constraint may represent a limitation for some use cases (e.g., malicious attack detection) where it is crucial to classify all the packets of the flow. To meet such a requirement, we designed a joint packet- and flow-level classification solution that for each flow can classify i) the first $n-1$ packets individually and ii) the n^{th} packet assigning a class for the whole flow (i.e., for all the following packets).

In the following section, we describe ii) the packet-level solution Henna, ii) advancements that we developed for Flowrest and iii) the joint solution.

6.1.1 Solution description

6.1.1.1 Henna

Previous works in the context of in-switch inference have shown that resource usage increases with the complexity of classification tasks. Indeed, the model size grows with the number of classes until it saturates the resources of the switch. In these cases, a bigger model that could have yielded better performances is just not deployable in the switch. In this context, we apply the concept of hierarchical classification to split a complex classification task into multiple simpler tasks. Such simpler models fit the resource constraints of the switch and, at the same time, collectively yield better performance than a single monolithic classifier.

Figure 21. Henna architecture mapped into the ingress and egress PISA pipeline.

We propose a two-stage packet-level classifier that splits a challenging task into simpler ones that can be handled more easily by smaller models. If we want to classify C classes, the idea is to form G groups of classes, with $G < C$, that are easier to classify in the first stage. For each group, then, a second prediction is made by smaller classifiers, which again need to choose between several classes $c < C$, yielding the final class of the packet. To achieve a more efficient allocation of switch resources, we deploy the first stage into the ingress control and the second stage into the egress control of the pipeline, as shown in Figure 21.

In the toy example shown in the figure, the first stage is represented by a random forest model, highlighted in dark blue color, which performs a binary classification, choosing between group A and group B. The prediction is then passed to the egress pipeline through the traffic manager by using a dedicated bridge header. In the egress control, the second stage is represented by two independent decision trees. The packet features are then matched against one of the two classifiers according to the prediction of the first stage. The final class of the packet is the prediction of the second stage classifier. The random forest and decision tree models are mapped into the PISA architecture with the state-of-the-art Planter [58] mapping. We want to highlight that, in principle, all the models could fit into the ingress pipeline. Nevertheless, due to the sequential nature of the PISA architecture, where multiple match and action units are executed one after the other according to the programmed logic, the trees of the second stage could not share the resources of the match and action units where the first stage trees are deployed. Deploying the second stage in the egress control instead avoids the problem and leads to better resource usage.

6.1.1.2 *Flowrest*

We designed a number of enhancements for Flowrest to i) enable the measurement of the latency of the solution and ii) improve its operation in terms of response time and memory usage.

To measure the average latency experienced by one packet traversing the switch, we exploited the timestamps provided by the Tofino Native Architecture (TNA). We used the time registered by the switch when the packet reaches the ingress ports and when it enters the egress control of the pipeline. As Flowrest has no programmed logic in the egress control, the difference calculated from these two timestamps gives us a very good approximation of the in-switch latency.

As described in Section 5.1.3 of D3.2 [2], after classification, the class information is stored in a dedicated register to avoid reclassification before the information is consolidated into the inference-aware forwarding block. Such a register is thus read for each packet traversing the switch to decide if the packet needs to be classified or not. Since in the TNA, registers cannot be accessed more than once per packet, the recirculation of each classified packet was necessary to access the register a second time. Although such a strategy was effective, it was not optimal as it forced each classified packet to traverse twice the switch, almost doubling the response time. To optimize Flowrest response time, we modularized the P4 logic to infer if the packet needs to be classified by just checking the flow packet counter. When the counter reaches n , it is sent to the inference module without checking the class information register and allowing it to immediately update the class information register.

6.1.1.3 *Joint classification*

We designed a joint packet- and flow-level solution that enables the classification of both individual packets and flows. Such a design fills a gap in literature where state-of-the-art solutions can classify either packets or flows. The solution design represents a challenge as it is not possible to just deploy in the switch one packet-level and one flow-level classifier due to the scarce memory available. For this reason, we designed a monolithic classifier that can perform both packet-level and flow-level classification. A toy example of our design is shown in Figure 22. A flow consisting of four packets is classified at packet level for the first three packets by leveraging the length of each packet as a packet-level feature and a constant value as a flow-level feature. The inter-arrival time of the packets is collected and the minimum value is stored. When the fourth packet arrives, the minimum inter-arrival time is finally used, together with the length, to classify the flow. During training, we assign to the fourth sample a weight four times bigger to reflect the fact that it is using a feature accumulated over four packets.

Figure 22. Joint packet- and flow-level classifier example.

6.1.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

6.1.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 24. RF models in programmable switches usage of the interfaces.

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	Through this interface, a complete performance and operational report is provided to the NIO about the in-switch classifier NIF.
Nio-Nifcm	This interface is used to allocate computing resources on programmable switches. The interface can be used to gather the classification results, the utilization of the memory and the experienced in-switch delay.
Nifm-Nifnis	Through this interface, a single in-switch classifier NIF can be instantiated, updated and terminated. Furthermore, multiple classifiers can be deployed into different switches, providing a distributed service.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface allows to change the ML model deployed into the programmable switch.
Nio-MLp	This interface is used to activate the retraining of an RF model if the classification performance is poor.
Mlo-Ncat	This interface is used to register a newly trained RF model into the catalog.
Nio-MANO	This interface can be used to provide real-time information about the classification performance, memory usage and the experienced in-switch delay.
Nio-Ext	This interface communicates to an SDN controller. As described in Section 5.1.5 of D3.2 [2], the envisioned controller is the Open Network Operating System (ONOS) promoted by the Open Networking Foundation.

6.1.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We describe how an in-switch classifier exploits the NIF management procedure discussed in Section 5.1.3 of D2.3 [3].

1. Under specific circumstances, a management procedure to change the classifier deployed in the switch can be activated. An example of such an event is the degradation of the classification performance.
2. A new classifier is trained with fresh data in case of poor performance.
3. The deployment of a new model is activated.

6.1.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 25. Flow-level Random Forest models in programmable switches. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
FR-IBSSI-000	Successful (100%)	The solutions shall learn network policies using the user plane itself. We perform traffic classification at line rate, paving the way to learn specific network policies for specific classes of traffic.
FR-IBSSI-001	Successful (95%)	The solution shall provide intelligence as a service to vertical 3 rd parties. Our solution encompasses interaction with the control plane where classification results can be potentially exploited by other services. Nevertheless, the data collected in the control plane must be considered raw data that cannot be immediately consumed by 3 rd party verticals.
FR-IBSSI-002	Successful (100%)	The solution shall integrate NI within programmable switches. Our solution performs inference fully in Tofino switches.

6.2 Efficient backhaul circuit switching

6.2.1 Solution description

The description of this solution was reported in Deliverable D3.2 [2].

6.2.2 Integration with the NI native procedures

6.2.2.1 Usage of the internal interfaces

Table 26. Efficient backhaul circuit switching usage of the interfaces

Interface	Purpose
Nio-Nifm	Through this interface, the switching configuration profile can be made available to the NIO.
Nio-Nifcm	Through this interface, new configuration can be communicated, and re-initiation of Birkhoff+ can be triggered.
Nifm-Nifnis	This interface will be used for the standard creation and termination procedures, as well as setting optimality gap ϵ to the switches, which will be used by the Birkhoff+ algorithm to determine the number of iterations.
Nifcm-Nivi	This interface can also be used to initiate different instances of the Birkhoff+ algorithm on the switches, according to, e.g., newly considered configurations/performance requirements.
Nio-MLp	N/A (not used by this solution)
Mlo-Ncat	N/A (not used by this solution)
Nio-MANO	N/A (not used by this solution)
Nio-Ext	While the solution presented here is, in principle, implementable on switch controllers, this practical aspect is not investigated here.

6.2.2.2 Usage of NIO procedures and elements

We describe how the switching calculation algorithm exploits the NIF management procedure discussed in Section 5.1.3 of D2.3 [3].

1. Under specific circumstances, a management procedure to re-initiate the Birkhoff+ algorithm in the switch can be activated. An example of such an event is the degradation of the switching performance due to a change in the topology.
2. The new topology is input to the algorithm.
3. The switching decisions from the new Birkhoff+ instance are activated.

6.2.3 Requirement satisfaction

Table 27. Efficient backhaul circuit switching. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.3	Status	Discussion
FR-IBSSI-002	Successful (100%)	The proposed solution in this subsection is not merely about data collection and pro-processing but also offloads decision-making to the data plane where the Birkhoff+ algorithm can be executed, and its decisions are implemented directly via the programmable switches.

7 Outlook towards 6G

The work done by this work package has been aligned directly or indirectly with the ongoing effort for the definition and the subsequent standardization of the 6G mobile system. In the following, we discuss how the DAEMON concept is aligned with them.

7.1 Access

The O-RAN Alliance plays a crucial role in the standardization of O-RAN technology, and its importance cannot be overstated. As telecommunication networks evolve and embrace new technologies, the need for more flexible, cost-effective, and interoperable network solutions becomes paramount. The O-RAN Alliance serves as a collaborative platform, bringing together industry-leading operators, vendors, and research institutions to drive the development and adoption of open and intelligent RAN architectures. As introduced in Section 4.2.1 of D2.3 [3], the integration of AI/ML workflows within the O-RAN architecture enabled DAEMON's NIP to manage Network Intelligence.

7.1.1 O-RAN Hardware Acceleration Abstraction Layer

RAN virtualization and orchestration is one of the key enablers for O-RAN architectures, given the flexibility and efficiency that general-purpose processors can provide to the overall virtualization platform. However, the virtualization of RANs brings multiple challenges due to the tight time deadlines associated with their operation. To properly address the aforementioned challenges, the O-RAN Working Group 6, Cloudification and Orchestration, dedicates multiple technical specification documents to define hardware acceleration abstractions, which essentially define how to integrate specialized processors, i.e., Hardware Accelerators (HAs), such as FPGAs, GPUs or ASICs at which applications can offload processing tasks.

The O-RAN O-Cloud Hardware Acceleration Abstraction Layer (AAL) serves as an interface between applications and hardware accelerators, facilitating the applications to be decoupled from the specific hardware implementations. This architectural approach allows for different options for offloading tasks to hardware accelerators:

- Look-Aside: The application invokes an HA to perform a specific data processing task and continues with other work (or waits until the HA has finished its work) while the HA is performing the requested task. This operation requires bi-directional communication for sending the task to the HA and for receiving the results from the HA.
- Inline: The application does not necessarily retrieve the processed data after invoking the HA. In this case, depending on the direction of the data, the application will either receive processed data from the HA without a previous request for data processing (Uplink), or request for data processing to an HA without retrieving the processed data after the HA has finished its work (DL)

NI solutions proposed by DAEMON extensively study the behavior of the default AAL and propose novel approaches and solutions based on network intelligence to effectively and efficiently address RAN virtualization and tasks offloading to HAs (Sections 3.1 and 3.2). The architectural novelties and NI algorithms may impact the design of architectural elements (e.g., the AAL) and the control loop procedures defined for future RANs.

7.2 Core

As discussed in D2.3 [3], Section 4.2.2, R16 establishes the groundwork for network automation, with a specific focus on the operation of Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) and presenting various use cases. In the following, we discuss the advances studied by WP3 in the context of the significance brought by R17 and R18 of the standard.

7.2.1 Release 17

Release 17 (R17) aligns with the architectural de-composition trends and divides the NWDAF functionality into two parts: the Analytics Logical Function (AnLF) and the Model Training Logical Function (MTLF). The AnLF is responsible for inference, reporting, and exposing analytics services, while the MTLF handles ML model training and exposes them to the AnLF.

R17 introduces several new capabilities, including aggregation from multiple NWDAFs, enabling analytics composition across network slices. It also introduces features like bulk data collection, data collection from the UE through a specific flavor of the Application Function (AF), transfer of analytics contexts or subscriptions due to UE mobility, and managing user consent for analytics.

To facilitate these enhancements, R17 introduces three new functions:

1. Data Collection Coordination Function (DCCF): Orchestrates the collection of data from 5G Core Network Functions (5G Core Network Functions) to prevent multiple NWDAFs from accessing the same data.

2. Analytics Data Repository Function (ADRF): Stores and collects data and analytics.
3. Message Framework Adaptation Function (MFAF): Exposes the services implemented by the NWDAF over a Messaging Framework, utilizing a pub-sub pattern like Apache Kafka.

Furthermore, R17 introduces five new types of analytics: Dispersion Analytics, WLAN Performance Analytics, Session Management Congestion Control Experience Analytics, Redundant Transmission Experience-related analytics, and Data Network Performance Analytics. This release, which aligned with the initial phase of the WP work, shared key concepts with the initial work discussed in D2.1 [58] and several working areas with this WP.

7.2.2 Release 18

Release 18 (R18) is the first release that goes beyond 5G (as it is branded 5G-Advanced) and enhances the operation of NWDAF in several ways. Firstly, it includes mechanisms for the AnLF to compute the accuracy of ML models and report it to the MTLF and service consumers. Secondly, the MTLF incorporates a similar mechanism to compute ML model accuracy and receive accuracy reports from AnLFs, which helps determine if an ML model requires retraining. Thirdly, R18 enables receiving feedback from service consumers regarding their actions that might have impacted analytics predictions. Fourthly, the MTLF gains the capability to generate and deliver multiple ML models for the same Analytics ID, allowing the AnLF to choose the most suitable one. Fifthly, R18 supports NWDAF Federated Learning, which involves training an ML Model across multiple decentralized entities without sharing local datasets. Finally, R18 facilitates NWDAF reallocation, as well as DCCF and MFAF reallocation.

R18 introduces additional functionality, such as support for roaming scenarios. This includes data collection by a Home NWDAF from a Visited NWDAF for outbound roaming users and data collection by a Visited NWDAF from a Home NWDAF for inbound roaming users. The ADRF's functionality is extended to store ML models as well. Moreover, a new Service-Based Interface (SBI) in the User Plane Function (UPF) provides a standard interface for collecting data from UPF. Additionally, finer granularity of UE location information is achieved by collecting data from Location Services (LCS) systems.

Lastly, R18 introduces five new analytics, bringing the total to 18: Packet Flow Descriptions (PFD) determination analytics, Location Accuracy Analytics, End-to-End Volume Transfer Time analytics, Relative Proximity Analytics, and UE-Route Selection Policies (URSP) enforcement analytics.

This release, hence, sets the architectural framework for some of the topics discussed in the project and for which we have defined the algorithmic solutions, such as the model re-training and the monitoring of the accuracy of the algorithm. Still, the DAEMON approach is much broader than the NWDAF and analytics framework of 3GPP, but it shows the overall compatibility of the solutions.

7.3 Management and Orchestration

The Network Function Virtualization (NFV) MANO has become a de facto standard for managing and orchestrating virtualized service deployments in 5G networks, with NFV as a prerequisite for resource and service virtualization. In particular, NFV is considered one of the key network transformation enablers, which started from the early LTE core network function virtualization based on virtual machines and landed on 5G by creating softwarized network cloud deployments based on containers. These deployments are nowadays orchestrated (monitored, created, migrated, terminated) with NFV MANO systems that contain only basic levels of automation. However, to move towards higher-order self-intelligent networking based on AI/ML and big data, the NFV MANO systems require more. According to ETSI [58], to implement an automated network management system, proper data management is the basis that will provide accurate, real-time, and reliable data, which can be reliably used to make decisions and act upon them. Nevertheless, enormous heterogeneity in terms of data sources, equipment, and service providers, which is present in 5G networks, will become even more challenging in 6G systems, which will open the path to more and more service providers and data sources toward further levels of automation and intelligence of networks.

To cope with the above-mentioned complexity, the following set of capabilities has been identified for future 6G management and orchestration systems [58]: 1) the adoption of the cloud-native principles also in NFV MANO system, 2) unified orchestration across an extreme edge-edge-core continuum, 3) unified MANO across multiple domains, 4) increased degree of automation (with no manual interventions in the process of service and network planning, design, deployment, optimization), 5) adoption of data-driven and AI/ML techniques in the MANO system, and 6) intent-based approaches for service planning and definition.

Thus, to make those capabilities achievable, ETSI is planning to pursue further simplification of NFV for the next decade [52]. This mainly refers to simplifying the interfaces of the existing NFV systems with a more declarative and intent-driven design, which will primarily simplify the use of network management interfaces and facilitate the integration of APIs produced by different vendors. Such intent-based

networking will also allow users who are not network experts (e.g., end-users or verticals) to deploy and set up their services by simply declaring their intents in a user-friendly and high-level manner. For this particular purpose, AI/ML functions deployed within 6G network intelligence stratum, either as NIFs or NISs, could be used to, e.g., guide the translation of these high-level intents into the corresponding low-level orchestration actions that will be executed by NFV MANO systems. These activities are very well aligned with the edge orchestration solutions discussed in Section 4.

Moreover, Future 6G systems are expected to connect a massive number of heterogeneous devices connecting to the network over a diverse set of network slices dispersed over an extensive computing continuum (extreme edge, edge, core, and cloud). This brings severe challenges to traditional NFV MANO systems, which are mainly centralized and manual, making it difficult for them to achieve high scalability and sustainability [58].

Thus, given the heterogeneity of Software-Based Architecture (SBA) of 5G and 6G systems, where most of the network functions (along with the application services) are virtualized and require proper configuration and management, it is essential to establish connected intelligence in terms of NISs and particular NIFs and to perform orchestration in an automated manner. This evolution toward automated MANO is expected to integrate AI/ML techniques into a closed-loop framework, which will create a fully autonomous NFV MANO that is capable of performing complex optimization and decision-making processes. Nevertheless, it is not realistic to expect that all NFV MANO operations can be optimized by applying a single ML model. This will, in turn, be realized as a set of suitable AI/ML techniques applied as NIFs and NISs, which are particularly focused on a specific task (e.g., mobility pattern, resource utilization, security vulnerability prediction). The outcome of such decisions will be harmonized and then jointly considered by NFV MANO, where the final decision on how and which MANO operation to perform is made.

Open Gateway is a GSMA-led initiative in the telco sector that seeks to transform communication networks into platforms. This will open telco capabilities in an interoperable, intuitive and programmable way. The GSMA Open Gateway initiative aims to accelerate industry support and collaboration to easily build new digital services and quickly and effectively deploy existing and new Web 3.0 services. GSMA Open Gateway APIs are defined, developed and published in CAMARA, the open-source project for developers to access enhanced network capabilities, driven by the Linux Foundation in collaboration with the GSMA.

A joint initiative of the Linux Foundation and the GSMA, CAMARA is structured as a global partnership to provide consistent access to network service features across heterogeneous operator and cloud infrastructures. CAMARA is committed to developing an open, global, and accessible API solution with access to operator capabilities, allowing applications to run consistently on telco networks, independently of the chosen provider and geographic location. The data-driven resource allocation solutions discussed in Section 0 promote this view.

8 Conclusions

The work carried out in WP3 targeted the integration of Network Intelligence (NI) for the Real Time Control directly in the VNFs. Following the requirements defined in WP2, WP3 designed 13 different NI solutions that can be categorized according to the specific subdomain of the network they target (T3.1, Compute-aware Radio Scheduling, T3.2 Multi-timescale Edge Resource Management, T3.3 Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces Control, T3.4 In-backhaul Support for Service Intelligence) and according to the network KPI they optimize (Reliability, VNF Energy Savings, Computing resource savings, Response time of AI-based NI algorithms, OPEX Savings, Wireless Capacity Increase).

Thus, WP3 work encompassed a broad area of the network, ranging from RAN operation to edge network orchestration, including novel solutions such as Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface or the integration of deep learning solutions directly into the switches u-plane.

All the solutions designed in the WP are integrated into the WP2 NI Orchestration framework. These have been accomplished in two phases: during the design, the split using the N-MAPE-K (Monitor, Analyze, Plan, Execute and Knowledge) framework allowed an easier integration with the NI plane proposed by the project and allowed the WP to promote additional requirements to be considered during the design of the NI Orchestration framework. In the deliverables, we showcase how all the proposed intelligent algorithms implement the different procedures and use the interfaces designed by WP2.

All in all, the work carried out by WP3 proved to be seminal for the next generation of mobile networks as recent initiatives in the context of SDOs, industrial, and research groups.

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